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Multimodal Analysis of James Bond Film Trailers (Based on “*On Her Majesty’s Secret Service*,” “*The Living Daylights*” and “*007: Skyfall*”)

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Abstract

The primary function of a film trailer is to advertise the film it represents and to create a compelling first impression that persuades audiences to view the film. This paper examines how various multimodal elements — including visual imagery, verbal dialogue, sound effects, and musical scores — contribute to a more immersive viewer experience and enhance emotional resonance and cognitive processing, thereby shaping audience perceptions of the film. The research employs qualitative analysis of selected trailers from the James Bond franchise. Through thematic analysis, this study aims to elucidate the significance of multimodal strategies in trailer production, ultimately providing insights into effective marketing practices within the film industry. By emphasizing the integration of diverse communicative components, this research seeks to advance the discourse on film marketing and narrative construction.

Keywords: film trailers, visual imagery, verbal dialogue, dynamic music, implicit context, multimodal texts, peak.

1 Introduction

The origins of film trailers can be traced back to 1913, when Nils Granlund, the advertising manager for Marcus Loew Theatres, innovatively spliced together rehearsal footage from the Broadway play *The Pleasure Seekers* into a brief promotional montage that screened after feature films. This marked the inception of the trailer industry, which at the time was rudimentary, as it was primarily managed by theatres and studios without fully leveraging the commercial and creative potential of trailers. The landscape shifted significantly in 1919 with the establishment of the National Screen Service by Herman Robbins. This company provided an outsourcing solution for theatres and studios, enabling them to delegate the creation of trailers. Robbins’ venture expanded the concept of trailers, allowing for more sophisticated marketing strategies and stylistic developments in the promotion of films (DiStefano 2015).

Films serve as one of the most compelling media for storytelling. The essential strategy for effective marketing lies in their emotional branding. Certain trailers succeed in capturing audience interest and inciting a desire to view the film, while others may fall short, failing to leave a lasting impression and becoming easily forgotten by consumers. This disparity in effectiveness highlights the importance of crafting trailers that not only convey the narrative essence of the film but also resonate emotionally with the target audience (Finsterwalder et al. 2012: 589-590).

When modelling the structure of film discourse, two distinct levels of communication must be considered. The external level encompasses the interaction between the collective author and the audience, whereas the internal level pertains to the dialogue among characters within the film. To facilitate this analysis, it is worth differentiating between ectocomponents and entocomponents. Film trailers are categorized as ectocomponents since they are products

of communicative activities that possess inherent meaning and semiotic significance. As ectocomponents, trailers are relatively complete and concise, with a primary focus on serving an advertising function (Shcherbak 2022: 54).

Film trailers have transitioned from simple promotional materials to complex multimodal texts that seamlessly integrate visual, auditory, and linguistic elements. As critical components of film marketing, these trailers not only shape audience expectations but also reflect and influence broader cultural narratives within the cinematic landscape. By employing a range of communicative modes — such as imagery, sound design, and textual cues — they engage viewers on multiple levels, eliciting emotional responses and fostering anticipation.

This paper aims to explore the distinctive characteristics of film trailers as multimodal texts, analyzing the application of key theoretical frameworks and the significance of iconic elements in modern cinema. By way of a case study, the aim of this study is to explore the impact of multimodal communication in film trailers for spy movies on audience engagement and understanding. Explicitly, the research focuses on how the effective integration of various modes of communication, such as visual imagery, verbal dialogue, sound effects, and musical scores, enhances the viewer's emotional engagement and cognitive processing. By investigating these elements, the study seeks to provide insights into multimodal strategies in creating compelling narratives that resonate with audiences, thereby contributing to more effective film marketing practices.

2 Literature review

A significant part of a film's social circulation is defined by its production as a commodity, initiated by the industry of which it is a part. A film's commercial status is more than a matter of money or profit. Film circulates as a product, not in a semantic vacuum, but in a mass-cultural environment teeming with related commercial significations (Klinger 1989: 5). Regardless of the genre of the broadcasted mass media (whether it is thriller, detective, comedy, etc.), most of them are intended to entertain the audience (Fekete 2017: 188). Although the main purpose and function of advertising is marketing (commercial), which is related to the promotion of the film product on the market, the trailer also performs an entertaining function; it draws attention to itself and to the film it presents. The trailer is a presentation of the film. It is a "microfilm" that reflects the best characteristics of the product and its genre (Fekete 2017: 188). Accordingly, if the trailer can entertain and thus interest the audience, the potential consumer expects the same reaction from the film product itself.

Trailers are the product of communicative activity, which has its content and semiotic form and is characterized by relative completeness and brevity. The semantic scope of a trailer to a certain extent coincides with the essence of the concept of "advertisement", which is modelled in marketing by the acronym AIDA, where A – Attention (attracting attention), I – Interest (excitement of interest), D – Desire (activation of desire), A – Action (incitement to action) (Shcherbak 2022: 55).

Trailers are a form of advertising, but they are also a unique form of narrative film exhibition, wherein promotional discourse and narrative pleasure are conjoined (Kernan 2004: 1). According to Hixson, trailers are "clips of film that are shown prior to the featured movie,

to advertise other movies” (Hixson 2006: 213-214). They are brief film texts providing a 1- to 3-minute cinematic experience that usually displays images from a specific film while emphasizing the quality; film trailers are created for screening in theatres to promote a film’s theatrical release (Kernan 2004: 1). Thus, film trailers are viewed as “samples” for moviegoers to decide whether they would like to purchase the film if the movie is from a genre they prefer, and they are an integral part of the cinema-going experience (Hixson 2006: 214). Kernan provides the analogy with “window shopping” where the audiences are “shopping” for films when trailers are presented as “free samples” of the films (Kernan 2004: 6). The main purpose of film trailer is to arouse the audience’s curiosity and expectations so that they could be persuaded to see the movie (Maier 2009: 159).

People have some expectations about what they will see when they go to the movies. Watching a trailer for the movie may play a role in a moviegoer’s demand for gratification (Hixson 2006: 211). According to Hesford, the characteristics of the trailer enable its multifaceted perception and indicate a cultural resonance that distracts the viewer from the specific commercial properties of traditional advertising. Thus, a culture of digressive reading positions film as a new form of cinematic expression, in which the negative associations with commercialism are transformed and used as a component of the performative effect, which provides implications for the further perception of the advertised film itself (Hesford 2013).

Nowadays, trailers are evolving from being assembled from discarded film footage to being created by specialized studios and trailer producers. This trend is called “Frankenstein,” which occurs when movie marketers work with production companies that make trailers for the movie. Thus, the marketers take several trailers made by multiple trailer production companies that have tested well and edit them together into a new trailer for the “Frankenstein” effect (Hixson 2006: 214). As a result, the product shall acquire a performative appeal in which the artistry of the presentation of the author’s composition and commercial manipulation are intertwined (Fekete 2017: 189).

According to Kress and van Leeuwen (2001), multimodality involves the integration of semiotic modes – such as image, language, sound, and gesture – into a cohesive discourse. Their framework, foundational for contemporary multimodal analysis, emphasizes that meaning is constructed not by a single mode but by the interrelation between them (Kress & van Leeuwen 2001).

The trailer’s dual function – as both advertisement and narrative – has been widely discussed (Maier 2009; Fekete 2017; Hesford 2013). Maier presents the idea of film trailer being “a multimodal text in which several semiotic modes are combined, and parts of texts created for other purposes are transferred, rearranged and supplemented in order to attain a promotional purpose” (Maier 2009: 159). The film trailer is a multimodal communicative artifact that combines diverse semiotic resources to achieve promotional and narrative purposes.

Film trailers mostly contain well-structured and well-selected shots, which inform and entertain potential audiences. Thus, the information conveyed in a film trailer has two contexts (Maier 2011: 144). The first context is implicitly promotional, which means that the information is relevant to characters and events. The second context is explicitly promotional, which covers information about the names of the file, directors, actors, and so on (Maier 2011: 144-145). The promotional information can be analysed in three dimensions (Maier 2009: 161).

The first factor is verbal: oral information is relevant to the advertised movie; meanwhile, spoken information, including words, sentences, and conversation, also needs decontextualization. The second is visual: it includes shots, scenes, subtitles, and transition effects appearing in a film. The third factor is auditory: it refers to speech, music, and sounds and their effect in the film trailer (Xing 2022: 18).

3 Methodology

Film trailers and standard advertisements have some similarities (Finsterwalder et al. 2012):

1) they both contain similar messages that highlight the offer’s features; 2) they comprise slogans and brands; 3) they use the producer’s or manufacturer’s reputation as a level to increase the attractiveness of the offer.

On average, movie trailers range from approximately 1 to 3 minutes in duration, whereas full-length films typically last between 90 and 180 minutes. This results in trailers constituting roughly 1-3% of the overall film length. Trailers serve as a crucial marketing tool, designed to generate anticipation and foster an emotional connection with the audience. Their concise length is carefully curated to showcase the most engaging and visually captivating moments of the film, effectively stimulating curiosity without overwhelming the viewer. Such brevity allows for a focused presentation that encourages potential audiences to seek additional information about the film or attend its screening.

Table 1. Percentage ratio between the length of the movie and the trailer (based on *007 James Bond movies*)

Name	Year	Length of the movie (mins)	Length of the trailer (mins.secs)	Percentage
Dr. No	1962	109	3.21	2.94%
From Russia with Love	1963	115	3.36	2.92%
Goldfinger	1964	110	3.09	2.68%
Thunderball	1965	130	3.10	2.38%
You Only Live Twice	1967	117	3.19	2.72%
On Her Majesty’s Secret Service	1969	142	3.49	2.45%
Diamonds Are Forever	1971	120	3.39	2.78%
Live and Let Die	1973	121	3.01	2.48%
The Man with the Golden Gun	1974	125	3.26	2.6%
The Spy Who Loved Me	1977	125	3.20	2.56%
Moonraker	1979	126	3.44	2.73%
For Your Eyes Only	1981	127	3.46	2.72%
Octopussy	1983	131	3.28	2.5%

A View to a Kill	1985	131	2.55	1.94%
The Living Daylights	1987	130	1.30	1%
Licence to Kill	1989	133	1.54	1.15%
Goldeneye	1995	130	2.42	1.86%
Tomorrow Never Dies	1997	119	2.30	1.93%
The World is not Enough	1999	128	2.19	1.71%
Die Another Day	2002	133	2.16	1.62%
Casino Royale	2006	144	2.30	1.59%
Quantum of Solace	2008	106	2.28	2.15%
Skyfall	2012	143	2.33	1.61%
Spectre	2015	148	2.41	1.62%
No Time to Die	2021	163	2.36	1.44%

Table 1 illustrates that, on average, trailers for James Bond films occupy between 1% and 3% of the total film duration. This proportion is justified by various factors, including marketing effectiveness, psychological impact, standard industry norms, and audience expectations. The concise nature of these trailers is designed to maximize engagement and interest while adhering to established practices within the film industry. By maintaining this relatively brief duration, filmmakers can effectively capture viewer attention and generate excitement for the forthcoming film.

For this study, we have selected three film trailers: *On Her Majesty's Secret Service* (Peter R. Hunt, 1969), *The Living Daylights* (John Glen, 1987), and *Skyfall* (Sam Mendes, 2012). These trailers were chosen to represent distinct eras in the *James Bond* franchise: the 1960s, 1980s, and 2010s, featuring different actors as Bond (George Lazenby, Timothy Dalton, and Daniel Craig, respectively) and varying lengths, enabling diachronic analysis of multimodal evolution in trailer production. This selection facilitates an in-depth examination of changes over time, though the narrow corpus of three trailers is acknowledged as a limitation that may restrict broader generalizations about the franchise; future research could expand the sample for greater representativeness. Among these, the first trailer is the longest, with a duration of 3 minutes and 49 seconds, while the second trailer is the shortest at 1 minute and 30 seconds. We have analysed the data gathered from these trailers through three dimensions: verbal, visual, and audial.

To ensure analytical reproducibility, the trailers were segmented according to Maier's four-stage model: prologue, orientation, complication, and evaluation. Each segment was annotated for verbal elements (e.g., dialogue, voiceover), visual elements (e.g., shots, imagery, transitions), and auditory elements (e.g., music, sound effects) using a qualitative thematic coding approach. Coding categories were derived iteratively from multiple viewings, with themes such as "conflict escalation" or "emotional arousal" emerging from data. Criteria for identifying "peaks" followed Thomsen and Heiselberg (2020), focusing on points of heightened arousal indicated by sudden increases in music tempo, shot pace, volume, or action intensity. Analytical decisions, such as classifying a scene as a "peak," were based on these observable multimodal clues to maintain transparency and allow for potential replication.

4 Results

According to Maier, in an implicit promotional context, movie trailers can be understood to consist of four stages: prologue, orientation, complication, and evaluation (Maier 2011: 144). The implementation of a four-stage approach in the analysis of film trailers can be justified based on its comprehensive framework for narrative construction and audience engagement.

4.1 *On Her Majesty's Secret Service*

The trailer for *On Her Majesty's Secret Service* has a runtime of 3 minutes and 49 seconds, accounting for 2.45% of the overall duration of the film. An analysis of the trailer, utilizing Maier's (Maier 2011) paradigm, is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Analysis of the film trailer for *On Her Majesty's Secret Service*

Stage	Time	Verbal	Visual	Audial
Prologue	0:00 – 0:53	<p>Voiceover: describing the atmosphere with Bond</p> <p>“An avalanche of action: bigger, better, <i>different</i>. Got to be, when he is around”;</p> <p>“Fabulous beauties, all of them dolls. everyone is <i>different</i>, they’ve got to be when he’s around”</p> <p>Bond: “My name is Bond. James Bond”</p>	 The first vision of the new James Bond	<p>Sounds: avalanche, fireworks, sounds of a fight, the prologue of “James Bond Theme” by Monty Norman</p>
Orientation	0:54 – 1:43	<p>Voiceover: “The different Double-O-Seven”</p> <p>“<i>The different</i> Bond from the same stake”</p> <p>“Diana Rigg as a Countess, a <i>different</i> Bond woman. This one’s got class. And style”</p>	 George Lazenby starring as new James Bond	<p>Sound: “James Bond Theme” by Monty Norman</p>

Complication	1:44 – 2:22	Narrator: “The villains with a <i>difference</i> ” “Telly Savalas as Blofeld, a new destructive force” Blofeld talking about his <i>differences</i> as a villain	 First glance on the main villain	Sounds: the shots of weapon, explosions.
Evaluation	2:23 – 3:49	Voiceover: “The creative skills of the cinema’s master filmmakers”; “If you think you know your Bond, think again. This one’s <i>different</i> . This one’s got hot”	 The title of the film	Sound: “All love in the world” by Louis Armstrong, “James Bond Theme” by Monty Norman

The movie trailer for *On Her Majesty's Secret Service* presents a largely explicit context (Maier 2011), which means it is focused on actors, film crew, and main characters, primarily highlighting the “new era of Bond” represented by the introduction of George Lazenby as the iconic character. The term “different” is notably reiterated throughout the trailer in various contexts, suggesting the creators intend to emphasize the distinctive nature of the “new” James Bond.

The prologue stage is an optional opening stage in trailers, and it usually suggests the tone of the story and presents a representative situation that could trigger the story’s subsequent development (Maier 2011: 148). The trailer opens with a prologue designed to engage the viewer, beginning with imagery of an avalanche accompanied by a confrontation featuring Bond, although his face is deliberately obscured.

The prologue concludes with the introduction of Bond, who delivers his iconic line, “Bond. James Bond” effectively transitions the viewer to the orientation phase of the trailer. This second stage contextualizes the narrative for the audience, providing essential background information specific to this film (Xing 2022: 21). The whole context that is sketched in the orientation stage makes it possible to understand the rest of the trailer (Maier 2011: 149). The primary emphasis during this phase is on showcasing the actors in prominence. The narration persists within the overarching theme of the “new Bond”, continually reinforcing the concept of “different” that has been established throughout the trailer, as shown in example (1).

(1) Voiceover: The different Bond from the same stake. Diana Rigg as a Countess, a different Bond woman. This one's got class. And style.

The third stage, complication, serves to introduce the central conflict of the film while offering additional detailed information about the narrative. This phase presents one or more actions that interfere with the main characters' lives, thereby intensifying the stakes and complicating their circumstances (Maier 2011: 149). In this segment, the viewer is introduced to the primary antagonist, thereby directing attention to Bond's imminent confrontation with Blofeld. This portion of the trailer features dynamic shootout scenes, enhanced by the auditory impact of gunshots, effectively creating a unique Bond atmosphere and fostering the viewer's recognition of the spy genre.

The evaluation section interprets the events and their potential outcomes. It can provide not one but several clarifications and interpretations of what has been presented in the previous stage or the outcome of those events (Maier 2011: 150). In *On Her Majesty's Secret Service*, the filmmakers are credited in a manner that showcases the film's artistry, prominently featuring descriptors such as “marvellous” and “simply stunning”, which are cleverly crafted from the initial letters of the film's title (see Figure 1). At this stage, the trailer refrains from providing clear interpretations of the outcomes; instead, it aims at cultivating an air of mystery and intrigue surrounding the film. This approach offers a subjective assessment of the film, positioning it within a certain context for the viewer, who must ultimately decide whether to engage with the film.

Figure 1. Screenshots from the trailer of *On Her Majesty's Secret Service*, 1969.

4.2 *The Living Daylights*

The Living Daylights, released in 1987, is notable for possessing one of the shortest trailers among the episodes of the James Bond franchise. Short film trailers fulfill several critical functions that contribute to their effectiveness in marketing, including enhanced audience engagement, highlighting unique selling points, and fostering emotional connections through storytelling. By creating excitement and anticipation, trailers engage viewers and stimulate interest in the film. They serve to spotlight distinctive aspects of the film, with research indicating that trailers which effectively emphasize unique attributes are more likely to resonate with potential audiences.

Moreover, short trailers are adept at building emotional connections with viewers, utilizing powerful imagery and sound effects to evoke strong responses. As Garrett asserts, “a trailer, cut well, needs to arouse, provoke, seduce and beguile” (Garrett 2012). This highlights the necessity for trailers to balance information dissemination with intrigue; when they reveal excessive details, viewers may feel as though they have already experienced the narrative, thereby diminishing their motivation to watch the film. Consequently, trailers should cultivate a sense of promise and possibility, tapping into irrational and emotional impulses that invoke desire and necessity (Garrett 2012). Garrett also presents a structured approach to film trailers akin to a three-act narrative framework. Act One establishes the film’s characters and setting, Act Two complicates their world by introducing various obstacles, and Act Three escalates the conflicts, thereby intensifying the excitement, tension, or humour (Garrett 2012). This structural approach not only enhances the narrative flow of the trailer but also maximizes its impact on the audience, cultivating anticipation for the full film experience.

By adhering to this intrinsic three-act structure, trailers can effectively entice viewers while encapsulating the essence of the cinematic work they promote, ultimately serving as a compelling precursor to the films themselves.

Table 3. Analysis for the film trailer for *The Living Daylights*

Stage	Time	Verbal	Visual	Audial
Prologue	0:00 – 0:18	Voiceover: “The name that means excitement is back. <i>Bond, James Bond.</i> ” Bond: “Believe me, my interest in her is purely professional.”	 First appearance of a new Bond's girl	“James Bond Theme” by Monty Norman, sounds of shooting
Orientation	0:18 – 0:31	Voiceover “Wherever he goes, adventure follows.”	 Bond and his new “adventure”	“James Bond Theme” by Monty Norman, sounds of explosion
Complication	0:32 – 0:56	Bond: “Two of our men are dead. Koskov’s named you.” Pushkin: “Then I must die.” Whitaker: “Kill him.”		“James Bond Theme” by Monty Norman, sound of explosion, shooting

Evaluation	0:57 – 1:29	Voiceover: “He lives for danger. He lives for the moment. He lives on the edge.” Bond: “Whoever she was, I must have scared <i>The Living Daylights</i> out of her.”	<p data-bbox="818 365 1177 443">The blood effect on iconic Bond’s appearance</p> <p data-bbox="818 616 1177 694">James Bond. 007. The Living Daylights</p>	“James Bond Theme” by Monty Norman, sound of explosion, shooting
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As shown in Table 3, the analysis of the trailer for *The Living Daylights* through the lens of Garrett’s narrative framework highlights the intricate structuring of cinematic trailers and their role in establishing character and themes within the film series. According to Garrett’s scheme, the prologue and orientation sections collectively constitute Act One of the trailers, wherein the introduction of the new James Bond, along with his new romantic interest, takes place. The iconic gun barrel sequence, a hallmark of the James Bond franchise, initiates this. This sequence, which is presented from the first-person perspective of a presumed assassin – effectively placing viewers in a position of agency – shows James Bond as he walks, turns, and ultimately shoots at the camera.

Notably, in the trailer for *The Living Daylights*, the initial portion of the gun barrel sequence occurs during the prologue, while a striking visual of a red blood wash — symbolizing the gunman’s bleeding — cascades down the screen during the evaluative phase, just prior to the final titles. This insight underscores the narrative and thematic significance of the gun barrel sequence, not merely as a stylistic flourish but as a fundamental component in establishing the visual and conceptual identity of the Bond films.

The complication segment of a film trailer serves as a critical juncture, often referred to as the “peak,” where the narrative tension and excitement reach a crescendo. Thomsen and Heiselberg (2020) articulate that a well-crafted film trailer typically employs a two-peak structure, featuring an initial peak occurring in the first half, preferably positioned early to capture the audience’s attention, and a subsequent peak towards the conclusion of the trailer. This structure is designed to optimize viewer engagement and sustain interest throughout the promotional piece. (Thomsen & Heiselberg 2020: 48). In *The Living Daylights* trailer, the transition to the first peak is facilitated using visual imagery and sound effects, particularly those invoking shooting and explosions. These elements serve to reinforce the action-packed nature of the film, prolonging the arousal experienced by viewers at this crucial moment. During this segment, the primary antagonists are introduced, enhancing the narrative stakes and heightening anticipation. The dialogue (2) within the trailer strategically employs a variety of synonyms for the term “kill,” thereby amplifying the dramatic effect and underscoring the menacing tone of the film. In the span of just six seconds, the trailer utilizes four distinct

terminologies for “kill,” demonstrating a deliberate choice to enrich the emotional and thematic resonance of the narrative:

(2) Bond (00:32 – 00:34): Two of our men dead. Koskov named you.

Pushkin (00:35 – 00:36): Then I must die.

Koskov (00:36 – 00:37): Eliminate him.

Whitaker (00:38): Kill him!

From the orientation to the evaluation phase, the strategic selection of action shots engenders moments of heightened tension that benefit from tight framing, thereby accentuating conflict. The utilization of varied shot types facilitates visual storytelling by presenting fragmented glimpses that collectively suggest a broader narrative arc. The narrative arc can be categorized into four distinct stages: establisher (E) – which sets up an interaction without direct action; initial (I) – which initiates the tension within the narrative arc; peak (P) – which signifies the apex of narrative tension and the point of maximal event structure; and release (R) – which allows for the resolution of the tension (Cohn 2013: 421). While these categories follow a prescribed order, it is important to note that not all stages are requisite within a sequence. In the trailer for *The Living Daylights*, various dynamic shots depicting perilous situations encountered by Bond are observable, including scenes of a plane crash, the explosion of a house, shooting sequences, parachute jumps, stunt performances, and a bridge engulfed in flames.

As shown in Figure 2, the concluding line delivered by Bond in the trailer prominently features the film’s title. Following this sequence, the imagery transitions back to the initial shot characterized by the iconic gun barrel sequence, now enhanced by the visual motif of red blood overlaying the screen. The title is displayed prominently in the final shot, accompanied by the names of the actor portraying Bond, the original author of the story, and the filmmakers involved in the production of the film. This compositional choice not only serves to reinforce the film’s identity but also emphasizes the collaborative nature of its creation, linking the cinematic experience to both the character of Bond and the creative minds behind the project.

Figure 2. Screenshot from the trailer of *The Living Daylights*, 1987

4.3 *Skyfall*

The trailer for *Skyfall*, released in 2012 to celebrate 50 years of James Bond films, has a runtime of 2 minutes and 33 seconds, accounting for 1.61% of the film's total duration. Unlike the previously discussed trailers, this one presents an implicit promotional context without emphasizing the actors or the filmmaking team. While *Skyfall* is not Daniel Craig's debut as James Bond, the trailer notably refrains from highlighting this aspect; instead, it directly showcases the film's main plot.

Table 4. Analysis of the film trailer for *Skyfall*

Stage	Time	Verbal	Visual	Audial
Prologue	0:00 – 0:19	Bond: "He is gone." M: "You both know what's at stake here." M: "Take the bloody shot."	 The beginning of the trailer – the missing part in the computer	Dramatic music with logical pauses, sound of gunfire
			 Moneypenny almost kills Bond	
Orientation	0:20 – 0:58	Mallory: "Three months ago you lost the drive containing the identity of every agent embedded in terrorist"		Dramatic music with logical pauses, which slowly comes to its peak. The

		<p>organizations across the globe.”</p> <p>M: “Where the hell have you been?”</p> <p>Bond: “Enjoying death.”</p> <p>Mallory: “Why not stay dead?”</p>	<p>In a rainy-day M writes an obituary for Bond, knowing he’s alive</p> <p>Explosion of MI6</p>	<p>sound of an explosion occurs at a moment when the music ceases, marking the peak of the trailer’s intensity.</p>
Complication	0:59 – 1:56	<p>Bond: “They went targeting her.”</p> <p>Severine: “How much do you know about fear?”</p> <p>Bond: “All of this.”</p> <p>Silva: “Mommy was very bad.”</p> <p>Bond: “Everybody needs his hobby.”</p> <p>Silva: “So what’s yours?”</p> <p>Bond: “Resurrection.”</p>	<p>First blink on the new villain</p>	<p>Dramatic music, sounds of gunfire and explosions</p>
Evaluation	1:57 – 2:33	-		<p>“James Bond Theme” by Monty Norman, plays during a</p>

			<p>Iconic scene – Bond with his new girl</p> <p>M meets an old friend</p>	<p>dramatic sequence that intensifies and reaches its climax toward the end of the trailer; sounds of gunfire</p>
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As exemplified in Table 4, the prologue begins with a scene in which Bond discovers a computer with a missing component, effectively drawing the viewer directly into the movie’s central plot. According to Thomsen and Heiselberg (2020), this segment serves as the initial peak to capture the audience’s attention (Thomsen & Heiselberg 2020: 48). Compared to the film, the trailer’s prologue effectively encapsulates the entire narrative, highlighting Bond’s initial pursuit of an unidentified villain and the subsequent gunfire that leads to his apparent “death”. From the very beginning, the trailer immerses viewers in the storyline. Given that one of the primary objectives of film trailers is to generate intrigue, marketers must include a suitable amount of narrative content (Moul 2007). While consumers may seek additional information to enhance their understanding of the film’s storyline, example (3) shows that the trailer should not disclose the entirety of the film’s content (Finsterwalder et al. 2012: 593).

(3) *M: You both know what’s at stake here.*

The orientation portion of the trailer furthers the narrative by depicting Bond being shot by Moneypenny, while M writes his obituary. However, the trailer suggests that M is aware of Bond’s survival. The atmosphere surrounding M is sombre, accentuated by the rain in the background, which adds a dramatic flair to the scene. Bond is seen emerging from the shadows, yet M recognizes him and greets him in her distinctive manner, as presented in example (4).

(4) *M: Where the hell have you been?*

This section serves as a representation of Act Two (Garrett 2012) and culminates in the explosion of the MI6 building, marking a peak in the trailer’s intensity. It effectively establishes a connection to the beginning, intertwining the storyline between MI6 and the unknown villain, who makes his first move in this confrontation. The viewer is subtly led to infer that the villain has a link to MI6, highlighted by the destruction of the building. Furthermore, the villain’s personal connection to M is underscored when he sends her a picture accompanied by the ominous message, *Think of your sins*.

The complication section of the trailer introduces a new character, Q, who was notably absent in the first two films starring Daniel Craig, *Casino Royale* and *Quantum of Solace*. In this instalment, Q is depicted as a young man, and Bond expresses his dissatisfaction with the new assistant before even getting to know him. The trailer emphasizes Q’s return as an iconic character by showcasing the gadgets and weapons he presents to Bond during their exchange

in the museum. Their dialogue (5) concludes with a handshake, signalling their readiness to collaborate in their mission to apprehend the villain.

(5) *Bond: Q.*

Q: Double-O-Seven.

Additionally, the complication segment introduces the villain directly, and the dialogue between Bond and Silva suggests Silva's connections to both MI6 and M. He refers to M as "mommy". as shown in example (6), highlighting a personal relationship and indicating that M is a significant adversary with whom Bond must confront. This interaction reinforces the characters' narrative tension and emphasizes the betrayal and conflict within MI6.

(6) *Silva: Mommy was very bad.*

The final segment is characterized by its exclusive use of non-verbal elements, presenting a fast-paced sequence of frames that emphasize shootouts and confrontations between characters, Bond's romantic interest, and M's meeting with the film's main antagonist. The brisk transitions between these frames generate a heightened sense of excitement and unpredictability. This stylistic choice is designed to evoke intrigue and compelling curiosity in viewers, encouraging them to engage with the full film to integrate these vibrant moments into a comprehensive narrative.

A notable feature of the *Skyfall* trailer is its use of dynamic music that adapts to the unfolding events. The trailer uses an adapted version of the James Bond theme song. The score intensifies during moments of high tension, while simultaneously quieting during dialogue or contemplative scenes where characters are faced with decisions. This musical arrangement blends seamlessly with the sound effects of the gunfight, creating an immersive experience. At the peak of the climax, marked by the explosion of the MI6 building, the music temporarily halts, allowing viewers to absorb the significance of the events depicted on screen. According to Leigh (1991), when the audio and video components of a message are congruent — meaning they are closely related — consumers are more likely to encode the message as a cohesive whole. This alignment enhances the overall impact of the message, facilitating better comprehension and memorization (Leigh 1991: 72). Film marketers utilize specific styles and tempos of music to convey the film's genre or establish a particular tone. This strategic choice significantly influences consumers' expectations regarding the content of the film, shaping their perceptions and emotional responses even before viewing (Finsterwalder et al. 2012: 590).

5 Discussion

In an analysis of three trailers of James Bond films, we found a consistent structural framework comprising four distinct stages: prologue, orientation, complication, and evaluation. The narrative nature of these trailers allows them to succinctly communicate the film's storyline while maintaining an air of mystery, which serves to engage and intrigue potential viewers. Trailers primarily fulfill a marketing function, aiming to captivate audiences and draw them into the cinema. Previous research indicates that trailers lasting between 1 to 3 minutes are

particularly effective at holding viewer attention and motivating them to watch the full feature. This duration accommodates the essential elements of the film, including its plot, principal characters, cast, and production team, thereby informing potential viewers without overwhelming them.

Movie trailers, akin to the films they represent, are multimodal texts that leverage various forms of communication. These trailers incorporate a diverse array of elements to convey their messages effectively. By engaging multiple modes, trailers create a rich sensory experience that enhances storytelling and captures the audience's interest, ultimately aimed at encouraging them to engage with the full feature. The analysis of three James Bond film trailers — *On Her Majesty's Secret Service*, *The Living Daylights*, and *Skyfall* — revealed that both verbal and non-verbal communication methods significantly enhance viewer engagement. The trailers effectively utilize musical scores, dynamic action sequences, sound effects, and vivid imagery to captivate audiences and draw their attention. This multifaceted approach not only enhances the narrative but also reinforces the emotional impact of the content, thereby increasing the likelihood of enticing viewers to watch the full film.

In movie trailers, the “peaks” play a crucial role, representing moments where the plot reaches its climax. Research indicates that the first peak typically occurs early in the trailer, aiming to capture the viewer's attention. This initial peak may reveal key plot elements to generate intrigue and entice the audience. Conversely, the second peak takes place towards the end of the trailer, heightening tension and spurring further interest. Modern trailers often achieve this second peak through rapid changes of shots, instilling uncertainty and posing unanswered questions that compel viewers to seek out the complete film. Simultaneously, the trailer concludes on a note of ambiguity, intentionally withholding certain plot details to sustain intrigue and encourage audiences to explore the narrative in its entirety.

While verbal elements and film dialogues can enhance a trailer, they are not essential for achieving the second peak. An analysis of the *Skyfall* trailer demonstrated that abrupt visual transitions, coupled with dramatic music, can generate significantly more tension than relying on text alone. The use of dynamic music is particularly pivotal in shaping the viewer's experience of a film trailer. In the action and thriller genres, trailers typically feature vigorous musical scores that contribute to a sense of momentum and narrative progression. These scores often incorporate strategic pauses and shifts in mood corresponding with changes in imagery, effectively enhancing the dramatic impact and reinforcing the emotional journey of the trailer.

6 Conclusion

The James Bond films prominently incorporate both iconic verbal and non-verbal elements, including variations of the signature musical theme, the iconic gunshot sequence, and the memorable line. These elements are strategically employed to cultivate a sense of cultural identity surrounding the franchise, reinforcing its branding while fostering an emotional connection with the audience. By leveraging these recognizable features, the films effectively engage viewers and enhance their overall experience. These elements serve to instantly signal to audiences that they are about to experience a Bond film, creating familiarity and anticipation that can draw viewers in. By incorporating these iconic elements, the trailers may evoke a sense

of nostalgia and connection to the long-standing history of the franchise, making them appealing to both longstanding fans and new audiences.

While film discourse is inherently multimodal, verbal elements of communication are crucial for grasping the plot's nuances. These elements encompass not only voice-overs featured in older trailers but also carefully selected pieces of dialogue that provide insight into the narrative without completely unveiling it. Depending on the specific nature of the film trailer, these verbal components can serve various functions, such as character description. For instance, the introduction of a new actor as James Bond can signify important changes within the franchise, reflected through the dialogue and voice-overs to inform audiences about the evolving character dynamics and storyline.

The film discourse research encompasses a wide array of topics explored by numerous scholars. Their certain aspects merit particular focus. The unique characteristics of film trailers significantly influence how studios select elements that effectively convey the essence of the film and deploy strategies that resonate with audiences. Investigating the verbal components of trailers within the spy film genre is crucial, given the specialized vocabulary that contributes to the overall atmosphere of these trailers. We identify valuable avenues for future research in examining the specific vocabulary employed in spy film discourse, as well as exploring effective techniques for crafting compelling film dialogues.

References

- Cohn, Neil. 2013. Visual Narrative Structure. *Cognitive Science*, vol. 37, no. 3. 413–452.
- DiStefano, Daniel. 2015. A Brief History of Film Trailers, or: Turns Out This Post Is Not About Peter Orner. *Michigan Quarterly Review*. Accessed December 10, 2024. <https://sites.lsa.umich.edu/mqr/2015/07/a-brief-history-of-film-teasers-or-turns-out-this-post-is-not-about-peter-ornor/>
- Fekete, Diana. 2017. Naratyv kinotreilera yak performatyvna interpretatsiia produktsii kinoindustrii (Movie trailer narrative as a performative interpretation of the film industry production). *Naukovyi visnyk Mizhnarodnoho humanitarnoho universytetu*, vol. 31, no. 3. 188–190. [In Ukrainian].
- Finsterwalder, Jörg, Kuppelwieser, Volker G., and De Villiers, Matthew. 2012. The effects of film trailers on shaping consumer expectations in the entertainment industry: A qualitative analysis. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, vol. 19, no. 6. 589–595.
- Garrett, Stephen. 2012. The Art of First Impressions: How to Cut a Movie Trailer. *Filmmaker Magazine*. Accessed November 26, 2024. <https://filmmakermagazine.com/37093-first-impressions/>
- Hesford, Daniel. 2013. “Action... Suspense... Emotion!”: The Trailer as Cinematic Performance. *Frames Cinema Journal*. Accessed November 13, 2024. <https://framescinemajournal.com/article/action-suspense-emotion-the-trailer-as-cinematic-performance/>
- Hixson, Thomas Kim. 2006. Mission possible: Targeting trailers to movie audiences. *Journal of Targeting, Measurement and Analysis for Marketing*, vol. 14, no. 3. 210–224.
- Kernan, Lisa. 2004. *Coming Attractions: Reading American Movie Trailers*. Austin: University of Texas Press.

- Klinger, Barbara. 1989. Digressions at the Cinema: Reception and Mass Culture. *Cinema Journal*, vol. 28, no. 3. 3–19.
- Kress, Gunther, and Van Leeuwen, Theo. 2001. *Multimodal Discourse: The Modes and Media of Contemporary Communication*. London: Arnold.
- Leigh, James H. 1991. Information Processing Differences among Broadcast Media: Review and Suggestions for Research. *Journal of Advertising*, vol. 20, no. 2. 71–75.
- Maier, Carmen Daniela. 2009. Visual evaluation in film trailers. *Visual Communication*, vol. 8, no. 2. 159–180.
- Maier, Carmen Daniela. 2011. Structure and function in the generic staging of film trailers: A multimodal analysis. In Piazza, R., Bednarek, M., and Rossi, F. (eds.). *Pragmatics & Beyond New Series*. 141–158. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Moul, Charles C. 2007. Measuring Word of Mouth's Impact on Theatrical Movie Admissions. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy*, vol. 16, no. 4. 859–892.
- Shcherbak, Olena. 2022. Kinodyskurs yak dvorivneva systema skladnykiv: funktsiinyi pohliad (Film discourse as a two-level system of components: a functional view). *Pomiedzy. Polonistyczno-Ukrainoznawcze Studia Naukowe*, vol. 6, no. 3. 175–181. [In Ukrainian].
- Thomsen, Morten, and Heiselberg, Lene. 2020. Arousing the audience: The two-peak structure of drama film trailers. *Journal of Scandinavian Cinema*, vol. 10, no. 1. 45–65.
- Xing, Qidan. 2022. Multimodal Discourse Analysis on a Cartoon Film Trailer *Up*. *Journal of Linguistics and Communication Studies*, vol. 1, no. 1. 17–26.

Audiovisual sources

- Hunt, Peter R. 1969. *On Her Majesty's Secret Service*. Eon Productions. YouTube. Accessed November 25, 2024. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dOLq5Rg9N-c>
- Glen, John. 1987. *The Living Daylights*. Eon Productions. YouTube. Accessed December 3, 2024. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IXAVKJTIM1E>
- Mendes, Sam. 2012. *Skyfall*. Eon Productions. YouTube. Accessed December 18, 2024. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6kw1UVovByw>

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Alienation, Identity, and Trauma in William Faulkner's *Light in August*

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Abstract

*This paper conducts a critical examination of William Faulkner's exploration of alienation, identity, and trauma in *Light in August*, drawing upon trauma studies and existential philosophy to scrutinise the existential anxiety permeating the protagonist's experiences. Central to this analysis is Faulkner's depiction of Joe Christmas, whose life is marred by profound alienation and psychological turmoil. The study expounds on how Christmas's past traumatic experiences, in tandem with societal rejection and marginalisation, fuel his ongoing struggle for identity and belonging. This relentless quest reflects deeper existential questions surrounding self-acceptance and connection, underscoring a universal human desire to overcome isolation and achieve self-understanding. By employing psychoanalytic and existential frameworks, the article provides an in-depth interpretation of Christmas's alienation and psychological crisis as emblematic of broader human concerns. Ultimately, Faulkner's portrayal of these existential predicaments within the context of the American South reiterates his ability to interweave individual and societal trauma, revealing enduring insights into the complexities of the human condition. Through this approach, the article enhances scholarly appreciation of Faulkner's literary contributions, offering a critical perspective on how his works confront fundamental issues of human identity, societal oppression, and the quest for meaning within a fractured world.*

Keywords: *alienation, identity, trauma, existential anxiety, William Faulkner*

1 Introduction

Light in August happens to be one of the major novels by William Faulkner. Published in 1932, it is set in the fictional Yoknapatawpha County in the American South and narrates the intertwining lives of several characters against the complicated backdrop of the American South, in a place and at a time where and when racial segregation was an integral pith to the Southern American experience. While the main narrative arc traces the journey of Joe Christmas, a complex figure with a mysterious racial background, the novel is also the story of Lena Grove, Byron Bunch, Luca Burch / Joe Brown, Gail Hightower and Percy Grimm. Though developed as separate individuals with no initial congruence to catenate them, the characters are linked by their traumatised and alienated psyches and their search for significance and identity as social outcasts. Their converging is made inevitable by psychical proclivities which ostensibly steer them towards an inexorable spiral.

Alienation, a feeling of disassociation engendered by estrangement, exclusion, or withdrawal, suffuses the separate and collective lives of characters who are driven by societal bigotry and traumatic experiences. Alienation, according to Schacht (1996: 10), is "the loss or absence of identification with, and participation in, the form of life characteristic of one's society." Since the 20th century, the various synonyms and concepts related to alienation have come to dominate the discourse on human relationships. Scholarly inquiries into the psyches of individuals described as "estranged," "peripheral," "compulsive," "atypical," "detached" and "solitary" underscore the pre-eminence of the tropes of alienation in contemporary literature. These studies, from disciplines such as philosophy to sociology (See, for example,

Baum 1975; Geyer 2001; and Ghosh 2017; Martin and Stack 1983; Schwartz 2017), collectively highlight the pervasive concern with apprehending the myriad dimensions of alienation within the context of modern existential social dynamics. Schacht further deconstructs this, noting that:

Ours is a world in which monolithic societies are sustainable only by totalitarian means. The globe has shrunk, economic life has become internationalised and popular culture is following suit, tourism is everywhere, travel is routine, and great numbers of people are on the move, for reasons both good and dismaying. Successive waves in communications technology are further rapidly eroding the conditions of isolation upon which the local acculturation process has long depended. (1996: 3)

Alienation in the early 20th century stemmed from a synthesis of socio-economic, political, and cultural factors. Rapid industrialisation and urbanisation disrupted traditional modes of existence (religion, community, family, class, gender, and nation), disintegrating previously cohesive rural communities and creating impersonal urban environments. This transition fostered widespread feelings of disjunction and isolation, leading to “a sense of weakened attachment to the central institutions in society” (Weakliem and Borch 2004: 415). Capitalist economic structures, with their focus on efficiency, often marginalised worker autonomy by reducing labour to monotonous, specialised tasks, thus exacerbating estrangement. Modernist intellectual and cultural movements reflected and amplified these sentiments, frequently depicting a fragmented and disenchanting reality. The aftermath of World War I further escalated disillusionment, dismantling prevailing ideologies and precipitating an existential crisis. Collectively, these factors reshaped the socio-cultural landscape of the early 20th century (See Bantock 1973; Curtnutt 2018; Flynn 2006; Josipovisi 2010; Levenson 1999; McDonald 2007; Owoye 2010; Ogunrotimi 2014). Although anarchist movements (drawing on the writings of William Godwin in England, Wilhelm Weitling in Germany, and Pierre-Joseph Proudhon in France) attacked the hierarchical authority of monarchies, governments, and corporations, they could not halt the development and expansion of depersonalised political and economic institutions from the 20th century onward.

Identity is a major construct in the modern novel, as characters navigate challenges of self-definition and belonging amid turbulent life experiences, in terms of race, gender, class, religion and nation. The early 20th century saw shifts in identity due to rapid industrialisation, urbanisation, and socio-cultural changes. As traditional social structures eroded, growing urban environments fostered dislocation and fragmented selfhood. The mass movement of individuals from diverse racial and cultural backgrounds disrupted societal monoliths, creating conditions that foreshadowed irreversible multiculturalism. The modernist construct emphasised alienation and the search for meaning, reflecting existential ambiguity in a world that had become increasingly chaotic in its nebulosity. The devastation of World War I was symbolic, as it intensified identity crises, fostering widespread scepticism toward the few enduring creeds that had been used to build up pre-war identity stereotypes, while rising nationalist movements highlighted political dimensions of identity. These upheavals (political, social, cultural) reshaped conceptualisations of selfhood, leaving a lasting impact on the early 20th-century socio-cultural landscape (Coetzee & Shevin-Coetzee 1995).

Trauma, perhaps, serves as the linchpin connecting the motifs of alienation and identity, leaving an indelible mark on the characters in 20th-century literature. If trauma can be caused by “extreme differences of wealth, status, and power that facilitate oppression, abuse, and scapegoating concerning class, gender, race, or species” (LaCapra 2014: xi), these constructs

have become the central problematics of human existence. The early 20th century saw trauma emerge as a critical concern due to World War I's unprecedented violence and devastation, leading to widespread psychological scars and recognition of PTSD (shell shock) (Fussell 2000; Warwick 1991). This period also marked the rise of Freud's psychoanalytic theories, which heightened awareness of trauma's deep-seated effects on behaviour and mental health. The interwar period's social and economic volatility, including the Great Depression, further compounded collective anxiety. Modernist literature and art explored concepts of fragmentation and psychological distress, underscoring trauma's pervasive impact. Consequently, there was an increasing recognition of trauma's profound influence on both individual and societal dynamics, reshaping mental health understanding.

This research provides an in-depth examination of William Faulkner's *Light in August*, deconstructing his exploration of alienation, identity, and trauma within a racially configured Southern society. By applying trauma and existential theories, we aim to deepen understanding of the protagonist, whose struggles against societal prejudices and search for self-identity reflect far-reaching socio-cultural and psychological dilemmas. We hope to contribute to Faulknerian scholarship by illuminating the protagonist's profound psychological and existential struggles, foregrounding the pernicious effects of racism and marginalisation, and examining enduring issues of identity crises and stigmatisation. Ultimately, we aim to underscore the universal human longing for connection and self-discovery, reinforcing the enduring relevance of Faulkner's work in modern existential and psychological contexts.

2 Trauma Theory: Disrupting Temporality and Selfhood

Trauma theory, rooted in psychoanalytic and post-structuralist thoughts, postulates that traumatic experiences disrupt the rectilinear temporality and cohesive narrative of the self. Trauma, as articulated by scholars such as Cathy Caruth, Shoshana Felman, and Dori Laub, fractures the continuity of experience, creating a temporal fissure that resists integration into the coherent narrative of the individual. Caruth laid the foundation for trauma theory in the introductory essay to *Trauma: Explorations in Memory* (1995), saying:

The pathology cannot be defined either by the event itself - which may or may not be catastrophic, and may not traumatise everyone equally - nor can it be defined in terms of a distortion of the event, achieving its haunting power as a result of distorting personal significances attached to it. The pathology consists, rather, solely in the structure of experience or reception: the event is not assimilated or experienced fully at the time, but only belatedly, in its repeated possession of the one who experiences it. To be traumatised is precisely to be possessed by an image or event. (4-5)

In her seminal work, *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History* (1996), Caruth spotlights the paradoxical nature of trauma: an event not fully experienced at the time but returning insistently as intrusive memories and flashbacks. She deconstructs temporal disjunction as intrinsic to traumatic experience, characterised by fragmented, non-linear memory that resists integration into a cohesive narrative. Caruth contends that trauma disrupts temporal perception, with past traumatic events incompletely apprehended during their occurrence but repeatedly re-experienced later. Thus, being traumatised means being persistently haunted by memories or images of the event. This phenomenon, expressed through

deferred action, “belatedness” (92), creates a temporal aporia where the traumatic past continually intrudes upon the present, leaving the event unassimilated and the present chaotic.

This disjunction highlights trauma’s inaccessibility and incomprehensibility, defying integration into cognitive and temporal frameworks. Consequently, the traumatised subject inhabits a paradoxical temporality where the traumatic past is neither wholly past nor entirely present but is continuously re-enacted, collapsing conventional temporal boundaries. Caruth’s analysis underscores the limitations of traditional narrative forms in conveying trauma, prompting a re-evaluation of historiography and narrative structures to address traumatic memory’s disjunctive temporality adequately.

Trauma’s temporal disjunction significantly challenges the existentialist view of selfhood. Existentialism, notably in Jean-Paul Sartre’s works, emphasises self-definition through conscious choice and commitment. However, trauma theory complicates this by underscoring the limits of agency and how trauma can undermine control over self-narrative. The unassimilated traumatic event haunts the subject, rendering self-construction fraught with interruptions and gaps.

2.1 Existentialism: Freedom, Responsibility, and Sartre’s Notion of “Self” and “Other”

Existentialism, as a philosophical movement, emerged in the mid-20th century, with figures like Jean-Paul Sartre, Martin Heidegger, and Albert Camus at its forefront. It grapples with fundamental questions of human existence, such as the nature of freedom, the burden of responsibility, and the confrontation with the absurd. Sartre’s existentialism is articulated in works like *Being and Nothingness* (2003) and *Existentialism is a Humanism* (2007). He posits in the latter that existence precedes essence, meaning individuals are not born with predetermined purposes or identities but must forge their essence through actions and choices. This elaborates the concept that human existence is contingent upon human actions, foregrounding its unpredictable and uncertain nature. This existentialist bend challenges traditional notions of human nature while highlighting individual autonomy and responsibility in configuring their meanings and significance.

Sartre’s framework, as presented in *Being and Nothingness*, is concerned with the interplay between “self” and “other,” explicating themes such as freedom, responsibility, and the dynamics of human relationships. At its core lies his assertion that existence precedes essence, emphasising individual consciousness and agency in defining one’s existence rather than being predefined by external factors.

Central to Sartre’s exploration of “self” and “other” is the concept of “the Look” (i.e., regard), which serves as a pivotal metaphor for the existential encounter between individuals or between an individual and society. This notion underscores how the gaze of another can objectify and reduce the subject to a mere object within the other’s perception. This encounter disrupts the individual’s sense of self, triggering an identity crisis as one becomes aware of being viewed and judged externally. The subject-object dichotomy inherent in “the Look” challenges subjective freedom and autonomy, highlighting the existential tension between being-for-itself (*pour-soi*) and being-for-others (*pour-autrui*). Sartre’s famous aphorism, “L’enfer, c’est les autres” (Hell is other people, in the play *No Exit*, 1989), encapsulates the anguish stemming from this intersubjective encounter. It reflects the existential dilemma wherein the presence of others imposes a dualistic framework upon the self, compelling individuals to negotiate between authentic self-definition and the external demands projected onto them by society.

Furthermore, Sartre critiques the phenomenon of “bad faith” (*mauvaise foi*, explicated in Part 1, Chapter 2 of *Being and Nothingness*) as a form of self-deception in which individuals evade their existential freedom and responsibility by averting “one’s gaze from facts, or options and choices, that at some level one knows to exist, but about which it is more convenient to be ignorant” (Blackburn 2005: 34). This evasion can manifest through denying one’s freedom by attributing actions to external factors or conforming to societal roles and identities imposed from without, thereby obscuring authentic self-determination.

Authenticity, in Sartrean terms, entails embracing existential freedom and responsibility to actively define oneself through choices and actions. Relationships with others become pivotal sites of existential tension where individuals negotiate subjective freedom amidst the intersubjective constraints and influences of social interaction. Recognition by others plays a crucial role in shaping identity but also poses a threat to existential freedom when it imposes external definitions and expectations.

In conclusion, Sartre’s analysis of “self” and “other” offers a profound exploration of human subjectivity within existential philosophy. His framework challenges individuals to confront the complexities of intersubjective relations, the struggle for authentic self-definition, and the constant negotiation of freedom and responsibility in defining identity amidst the gaze and expectations of others. This inquiry signposts as a compelling critique of how social dynamics shape individual existence and the existential ramifications of interpersonal encounters.

2.2 *The Convergence of Trauma, Existentialism, and Intersubjectivity*

The intersection of trauma theory, existentialism, and Sartre’s notion of “self” and “other” provides a fertile ground for exploring the complexities of human subjectivity and relationality. Trauma, with its disruptive force, challenges the existentialist ideal of coherent self-construction. The traumatic event, in its return and repetition, fractures the individual’s sense of agency and continuity, rendering the project of self-definition an arduous and often Sisyphean task. According to Sartre, the impact of the past (as trauma assails the present) is huge, and it “is not a subjective nuance which comes to shatter the memory; it is an ontological relation which unites the past to the present ... (the) past never appears isolated in its pastness” (2003: 133). In his elaboration, Flynn asserts that:

That relation is not external, it is internal and constitutive. I “am” my past, I don’t simply have it. But this past has an identity and a permanence that is ever increasing as I continue to live. Its ontology is factual; it assumes the features of being-in-itself. So I am my past in the manner of not-being it. (2014: 196)

As Sartre deconstructs in *Being and Nothingness*, the past plays a pivotal role in configuring human consciousness and existential experience. He posits that memory is an active cognitive process integral to present consciousness, wherein recollections are selectively assimilated and occasionally distorted. The past is not inert but perpetually revisited and reinterpreted, complicating notions of a static self. Crucially, Sartre introduces “bad faith,” where individuals may falsify their freedom by subscribing uncritically to societal norms, leveraging past circumstances as rationalisations for present conduct. Amid these influences, Sartre underscores the significance of existential choice, affirming the freedom to select one’s actions independent of past determinants. The intersubjective dimension of trauma complicates this

schema, as trauma is embedded in social contexts. The “look” of the other can re-inscribe individuals in narratives of victimhood. Conversely, recognizing the other’s humanity and empathetic engagement offer pathways for healing, enabling survivors to reclaim agency and reconstruct their sense of self.

3 Alienation in *Light in August*

Light in August commences with a vivid depiction of Lena Grove, a pregnant woman from Alabama, resting by a Mississippi roadside with her feet submerged in a ditch as she clutches her shoes. After a month of travel, hitchhiking on wagons or traversing dusty paths on foot, she remains resolute in her determination to reach Jefferson. Lena believes that her lover, employed at a planing mill in the city, will marry her. She aspires to finally don her shoes upon arriving in the urban setting. This solitary image of Lena, burdened by pregnancy and pursuing a man she believes will give her life meaning, serves as a prelude to the novel’s central themes. The description of the wagon plodding along the road subtly symbolises the alienated lives of the characters. While the lives of other characters are more thoroughly explored, Faulkner lays the foundation for alienation through Lena’s presentation on that isolated, forlorn road:

The sharp and brittle crack and clatter of its weathered and ungreased wood and metal is slow and terrific: a series of dry sluggish reports carrying for a half mile across the hot still pinewiney silence of the August afternoon. Though the mules plod in a steady and unflagging hypnosis, the vehicle does not seem to progress. It seems to hang suspended in the middle distance forever and forever, so infinitesimal is its progress, like a shabby bead upon the mild red string of road. So much is this so that in the watching of it the eye loses it as sight and sense drowsily merge and blend, like the road itself, with all the peaceful and monotonous changes between darkness and day, like al-ready measured thread being rewound onto a spool. So that at last, as though out of some trivial and unimportant region beyond even distance, the sound of it seems to come slow and terrific and without meaning, as though it were a ghost travelling a half mile ahead of its own shape. (5-6)

The last part of the above quotation (“a ghost travelling a half mile ahead of its own shape”) metaphorises the experiences of most of the characters. Alienation, a pervasive motif in the novel, profoundly impacts the lives of its characters, particularly the primary figure, Joe Christmas, whose life Farrell (1995: 84) says is “heaped with injustice” and “dark satanic mills that have figured prominently in Joe’s childhood” (Rampton 2008: 69). This pervasive sense of alienation undergirds the extent to which societal expectations and personal histories contribute to his estrangement and disconnection from whichever community he finds himself.

Christmas’s alienation begins in early childhood, marked by abandonment and rejection. Found on the doorstep of an orphanage on Christmas Day, he is named “Christmas,” symbolising his identity as an unwanted gift. The orphanage, meant to be a refuge, becomes the first site of his social alienation, where the other children “have been calling him Nigger for years” (125). His early exposure to racial prejudice occurs when his “supposed” grandparents claim he is the product of a relationship between their daughter, Milly Hines, and a Mexican, later suggesting that his father might be black. Even the dietician, operating under the conviction that Christmas has caught her while she was breaching moral and professional

propriety, retaliatorily racializes him as Black, a discursive act that initiates a chain of psychological and institutional violences, ultimately resulting in his expulsion.

The critical scene in which Christmas is punished for overhearing the dietitian's sexual encounter accentuates his premature exposure to adult complexities and his enforced separation from innocence. This event not only precipitates his departure from the orphanage but also instils in him a deep sense of shame and displacement. Faulkner introduces Christmas as a figure of liminality, perpetually existing at the margins of societal norms and expectations.

It is unsurprising that early in the novel, the other characters know nothing about him ("They did not know him at all," 27), as he has lived a peripatetic life. After leaving home at seventeen, he wandered for sixteen years before arriving in Jefferson, refusing to develop a specific identity or maintain stable relationships. Tragically, even at the end of the novel, he remains inscrutable to others, just as he was at the beginning. However, according to Byron (a mill worker who tries to help Christmas), if Christmas's behaviour does not signal danger to those around him, the very sound of his name should have indicated something imminently destructive:

It seemed to him that none of them had looked especially at the stranger until they heard his name. But as soon as they heard it, it was as though there was something in the sound of it that was trying to tell them what to expect; that he carried with him his own inescapable warning, like a flower its scent or a rattlesnake its rattle. Only none of them had sense enough to recognise it. (29)

Though Joe Christmas's life is marked by a sense of perpetual motion, reflecting his internal disquiet and search for belonging, his nomadic existence is symbolic of his alienation. As the narrator reveals, there is "something definitely rootless about him, as though no town nor city was his, no street, no walls, no square of earth his home" (27). He drifts from place to place, never staying long enough to form meaningful connections or to establish a sense of home. This rootlessness is a physical manifestation of his internal temper, highlighting the theme of existential displacement that pervades the novel:

He thought that it was loneliness which he was trying to escape and not himself. But the street ran on: catlike, one place was the same as another to him. But in none of them could he be quiet. But the street ran on in its moods and phases, always empty: he might have seen himself as in numberless avatars, in silence, doomed with motion, driven by the courage of flagged and spurred despair; by the despair of courage whose opportunities had to be flagged and spurred. He was thirty three years old. (93)

Christmas feels like a perpetual outsider, looking at others from the outside as he is never welcomed or happy sticking with any side of the racial divide.

The episode in which Christmas works at the mill and his subsequent relationship with Joanna Burden further elucidate this trope. Joanna's house, located on the outskirts of the town, symbolises a liminal space where Christmas's alienation intensifies. Joanna herself, an outcast due to her Northern background and her family's abolitionist history, mirrors Christmas's alienation. Their relationship, characterised by cycles of passion and violence, serves as a microcosm of Christmas's larger struggle with estrangement and belonging. Because they are both alienated, they remain inscrutable to each other, offering little protection against the world:

She told him very little, anyway. They talked very little, and that casually, even after he was the lover of her spinster's bed. Sometimes he could almost believe that they did not talk at all, that he didn't know her at all. It was as though there were two people: the one whom he saw now and then by day and looked at while they spoke to one another with speech that told nothing at all since it didn't try to and didn't intend to; the other with whom he lay at night and didn't even see, speak to, at all. (96)

Rather than providing the much-needed acceptance to each other, they probably reflected a deeper level of estrangement that further foregrounded and increased their personal trauma. Whatever succour they found in or provided for each other was temporary, as they could neither deny nor escape the centrality of the trauma they felt it in their lives:

Sometimes he could almost believe that they did not talk at all, that he didn't know her at all. It was as though there were two people: the one whom he saw now and then by day and looked at while they spoke to one another with speech that told nothing at all since it didn't try to and didn't intend to; the other with whom he lay at night and didn't even see, speak to, at all. (219)

Indeed, their coming together only served to accentuate their alienation within the temporary security and consolation provided by the circumstance of having someone to relate with. One is not surprised to discover that Christmas's nomadic experience has not provided him with enough stability to imbibe the requisite psychological intricacies needed to formulate relationships, hence that "she more than shocked him: she astonished and bewildered him. She surprised and took him unawares ... he thought she was under a delusion...he thought that she was mad" (244-245). On her part, she sees her relationship with him as her own attempt at personal perdition, though an escape from "her whole past life, the starved years" (250).

Joe Christmas's alienation is exacerbated by his experience within a liminal space configured by racial-cum-social disjunction. His ambiguous racial identity, fluctuating between blackness and whiteness, situates him as an eternal outcast, incapable of being fully integrated into the sociocultural constructs of either collective. This racial ambiguity engenders a disruption of subjectivity, amplifying the estrangement characterising his engagements with a society pivoted around inflexible demographic dichotomies. Within the white community, he is subjected to institutional racism and rejection, perceived exclusively through the prism of blackness, while the black community keeps an emotional distance, sensing his detachment and liminal essence.

Christmas's interpersonal relationships further demonstrate the complexity of his demographic liminality, as he is continually positioned in a state of transition between potential acceptance and inexorable rejection. His tempestuous interactions with women and authority figures gird his incapacity to reconcile the splintered dimensions of his identity, with every fleeting prospect of integration collapsing under the stifling gravity of societal norms. This unrelenting swing between repudiation and ephemeral acceptance escalates his alienation, disallowing any steady construction of self or affiliation. Ultimately, Christmas's existence within this marginal in-betweenness accentuates his existential anguish and isolation, as his alienation materialises not solely from external societal rebuff but also from his internalised battle with his own variable racial identity.

4 Identity in *Light in August*

In *Light in August*, the theme of identity is intricately woven into the character of Joe Christmas, whose search for self-definition and belonging drives the narrative. Christmas's ambiguous racial identity serves as a focal point for his existential internal conflict and external struggles, highlighting the complexities of identity in the racially charged South.

In the words of Mathews (2009), the novel depicts critical "areas of social life undergoing change in the modern South: relations between sexes and relations between races" (160). Christmas's indeterminate race prevents him from finding a stable place in a society stratified along racial lines. His assertion that "I don't know it" (240) if his father was black signposts the depth of his liminality; he is stuck in a space where there are no discernibly stable sociocultural constructs. His refusal to acknowledge any black heritage and insistence on identifying as white when it suits him reflect his internal conflict and awareness of the harsh realities of racial hierarchy. "Sometimes he would remember how he had once tricked or teased white men into calling him a negro in order to fight them, to beat them or be beaten; now he fought the negro who called him white" (92-93). This ambiguity becomes a source of profound alienation. Christmas is caught between two worlds, unable to fully embrace either. His relationships with women, particularly with Bobbie, the waitress he loves, and Joanna Burden, the older woman who becomes his lover, are fraught with tension and violence, revealing his deep-seated anger and confusion. These relationships underscore his inability to connect on a human level, further emphasising his existential isolation. Faulkner uses Christmas's violent tendencies to illustrate the internalisation of societal frustration. The brutality he exhibits is a manifestation of his inner turmoil and the external pressures of a racially prejudiced society. His violent outbursts are not merely acts of defiance but also desperate attempts to assert his identity in a world that continuously denies his humanity.

The name "Joe Christmas" extends beyond mere designation; it evinces his lack of background, connections, and distinct identity. It intimates that he is viewed as a tabula rasa, a vessel onto which others can project any imaginable character and manipulate him into embracing it. From a young age, Christmas grapples with the burden of his mixed-race heritage, never fully accepted by either black or white communities:

The newcomer turned without a word. The others watched him go down to the sawdust and vanish and appear with a shovel and go to work. The foreman and the superintendent were talking at the door. They parted and the foreman returned. "His name is Christmas," he said.

"His name is what?" one said.

"Christmas."

"Is he a foreigner?"

"Did you ever hear of a white man named Christmas?" the foreman said.

"I never heard of nobody a-tall named it," the other said. (29)

This lack of belonging fuels his sense of alienation and self-loathing, leading him to reject any racial identity and attempt to be assimilated into white society. However, his efforts are not only half-hearted but futile, as he is ultimately denied acceptance due to his perceived difference.

When Joe Christmas suddenly appears in the town three years before Lena, he stands out in almost every imaginable aspect:

And the group of men at work in the planer shed looked up and saw the stranger standing there, watching them. They did not know how long he had been there. He looked like a tramp, yet not like a tramp either. His shoes were dusty and his trousers were soiled too. But they were of decent serge, sharply creased, and his shirt was soiled but it was a white shirt, and he wore a tie and a stiff brim straw hat that was quite new, cocked at an angle arrogant and baleful above his still face. He did not look like a professional hobo in his professional rags, but there was something definitely rootless about him, as though no town nor city was his, no street, no walls, no square of earth his home. And that he carried his knowledge with him as though it were a banner, with a quality ruthless, lonely, and almost proud. (27)

Christmas's search for identity is further exacerbated by his traumatic past, which was marked by abandonment, abuse, and a lack of familial ties. Without a sense of belonging or connection to a family pedigree or heritage, he struggles to define himself and find purpose in a world that thrives on categorisation. His experiences with racism, violence, and betrayal shape his identity, leaving him disillusioned and disconnected from society.

Christmas wrestles with his identity amidst the racial biases ingrained by his grandfather, culminating in tragic consequences epitomised through Doc Hines's violent actions. This fixation on race intertwines with Calvinist beliefs, evident in figures like Calvin McEachern and Joanna Burden. Faulkner portrays these fixations as remnants of a dehumanising religion, symbolising the erosion of Southern values. Joe's pursuit of self-understanding is obstructed by societal hostility and persecution. He embodies the struggle of transitioning from a nebulous existence to a fully realised individual, especially within the racially charged environment of the South. Raised by a grandfather who treats him as if he is a convicted felon, he traverses a labyrinth of manipulation and hardship in his pursuit of self-definition. Enduring a spectrum of mistreatment, from betrayal to physical mutilation, he yearns for a place of belonging and autonomy. His passive disposition and vulnerability make him a poignant figure, constantly seeking refuge and a genuine sense of self.

Christmas's racial ambiguity and uncertain heritage profoundly shape his sense of self, fueling a relentless internal struggle and deep-rooted self-loathing. This lack of belonging leaves him adrift and unmoored, unable to reconcile his dual identity and plagued by an incubus-like sense of overwhelming otherness. Caught between two worlds, Joe struggles to find acceptance in a society that refuses to see him as he truly is. This internal turmoil manifests in destructive behaviour and pervasive self-loathing, as he seeks to escape the painful reality of his existence. His racial ambiguity becomes a metaphor for broader themes of identity and belonging, highlighting the devastating consequences of societal prejudice and the human cost of denying one's true self.

Christmas's struggle for self-identity takes a queer turn when we deconstruct one of his most revealing assertions in the novel. After affirming uncertainty about whether one of his parents was black and realising he has spent most of his life in rejection due to the belief that he has negro blood, he declares, "If I'm not, damned if I haven't wasted a lot of time" (241). This situation fundamentally undermines the stability and the integrity of social constructs within the community. In a society characterised by racial, religious, and class distinctions, where Christmas could ostensibly be perceived as white, his racial identity is not substantiated through demographic praxis but rather through oral transmission. This raises the critical question: if identity is so precarious and contingent, does it require tangible evidence, or could mere interpellations or questionable factoids suffice to dictate an individual's racial classification? While Christmas grapples with a laborious quest for self-identification, this

crusade seems destined for failure not due to emotional frailty on his part, but because of the magnitude of the opposition, which in this case is societal prejudice. According to Singal (1997):

Joe's prolonged struggle to achieve identity is in turn closely connected with another central and problematic issue in *Light in August* that of free will. On the one hand, it is clear that Joe is, in Alfred Kazin's words, "the man things are done to, . . . who has no free will of his own." More precisely, he is the victim of powerful social and psychological forces that largely determine his life, the ultimate example of a man held captive by the interlocking religious, racial, and sexual beliefs of his culture, which lodge in his unconscious during childhood and later dominate him without his ever being fully aware of their power. In the words of Lee Jenkins, "the very thoughts that he thinks about himself have already been determined." To this extent Joe has no control over his identity but rather becomes what his society insists that he be. Viewed from this perspective, he is a helpless pawn of his circumstances. (170)

As "a helpless pawn," without "control over his destiny," Christmas becomes a subject for contextual vagaries, a transient arriviste who refuses to subscribe to any connection to anyone or anything, and to the end "remained a foreigner to the immutable laws which earth must obey" (Faulkner 1968: 320). Ultimately, his refusal to accept societal categorisation, and his predilection for preferring the liminal space between the races is a form of social protest, which the society does not tolerate; "He never did anything. He never acted like either a nigger or a white man. That was it. That was what made the folks so mad" (331).

5 Trauma in *Light in August*

Trauma significantly impacts individuals' sense of self and belonging, often exacerbating feelings of alienation and triggering identity crises. Traumatic experiences, such as abuse, violence, or loss, disrupt one's sense of security, leading to emotional disorientation and existential uncertainty. Trauma distorts perceptions of trust and safety, inhibiting survivors' ability to form meaningful relationships and deepening their sense of isolation. This mistrust, coupled with an internal struggle to reconcile past experiences with present identity, results in profound identity chaos. Individuals may grapple with feelings of shame, guilt, and self-blame, further alienating themselves from others and reinforcing negative self-perceptions. For those from marginalised communities, trauma compounds existing feelings of exclusion, magnifying the impact of systemic injustice and societal stigma. Ultimately, trauma disrupts identity and belonging by inducing mistrust, distorting self-perception, and perpetuating feelings of shame and alienation. Recovery necessitates a comprehensive approach, addressing emotional, psychological, and social dimensions to foster reconnection and self-acceptance.

In *Light in August*, William Faulkner portrays a myriad of traumatic experiences endured by the characters, illustrating the profound impact of personal histories on individual psyches within the racially charged and socially repressive South. Christmas experiences a childhood marked by abandonment, abuse, and racial identity confusion. Raised in an orphanage after being abandoned by his grandparents, he faces rejection and ostracism from both black and white communities due to his ambiguous racial background. This sense of alienation and lack of belonging fuels his inner turmoil and self-destructive behaviour, ultimately leading to acts of violence and a desperate search for identity and belonging. Despite

having “seen and experienced” a lot, he is unable to develop strong attachments to others because of his inability to maintain any significant connection to anyone, anything, or anywhere.

The impact of a traumatic past on the present in an individual’s life is highlighted in the opening paragraph of chapter six, which takes the reader to Christmas’s childhood, specifically at five years old:

MEMORY believes before knowing remembers. Believes longer than recollects, longer than knowing even wonders. Knows remembers believes a corridor in a big long garbled cold echoing building of dark red brick sootbleakened by more chimneys than its own, set in a grassless cinderstrewnpacked compound surrounded by smoking factory purlieus and enclosed by a ten foot steel-and-wire fence like a penitentiary or a zoo, where in random erratic surges, with sparrowlike childtrebling, orphans in identical and uniform blue denim in and out of remembering but in knowing constant as the bleak walls, the bleak windows where in rain soot from the yearly adjacent chimneys streaked like black tears. (111)

This opening of Chapter 6 portrays young Christmas poised to surreptitiously access the dietician’s quarters at the orphanage, seeking to appropriate more of her toothpaste. Faulkner’s narrative prominently explores the enduring influence of memory on individuals, profoundly shaping their present and future. This theme constitutes a central focus within Faulkner’s extensive examination of his characters’ moral constitutions.

For many of Faulkner’s characters, the past embodies an inheritance characterised by hardship, suffering, degradation, and shame, a legacy that relentlessly pursues and metastatically shapes their subsequent lives. Christmas’s formative years are marked by a history of mistreatment and neglect, which manifest as memories possessing a potency surpassing any straightforward, objective recounting of his life’s events. Faulkner contends that even seemingly trivial occurrences, such as a child clandestinely appropriating toothpaste, can reverberate far beyond the moment of their unfolding. The orphanage’s austere and oppressive corridors delineate a psychological domain that Christmas internalises, carrying it as an indelible memory throughout his existence. Whether consciously acknowledged or not, these experiences endure as immutable fixtures in Christmas’s psyche.

Beneath the surface of recollection and contemplation lies a deeper stratum, wherein reside the profound and ineradicable wounds, both psychological and physical, that Christmas bears. It is this collective reservoir of memories, encapsulating a history of affronts and abuses, of rejections and persecutions, that fundamentally delineates his identity and ultimately contributes to his tragedy. The trauma inflicted on Christmas by his adoptive father, Simon McEachern, plays a crucial role in shaping his character. McEachern’s strict and abusive upbringing leaves Christmas emotionally scarred and resistant to authority, relationships or any form of sympathy or affection. The harsh discipline and religious fanaticism imposed by McEachern (who preached about “the superiority of the white race . . .,” 325) instil in Christmas a deep-seated resentment and a tendency towards rebellion. This abusive upbringing is a significant factor in Christmas’s development of a hardened and defensive persona. Brooks (1983) traces the origin of Christmas’s harrowing experience with the McEachern to an early age:

When Joe is eight years old, Mr. McEachern demands that Joe memorize the catechism. Joe refuses. His stubbornness more than matches that of his foster father. The ordeal begins before

breakfast on a Sunday morning and goes on past suppertime. Joe has no food, and, lying in his bed, wonders why he feels “weak and peaceful.” Later that evening, his foster mother slips up the stairs with a tray of food. She tells Joe that her husband does not know that she is bringing it. What does the boy do? He takes “the tray and [carries] it to the corner and [turns] it upside down, dumping the dishes and food and all onto the floor.” Then he silently gets back into bed. Long after she has gone, he kneels above “the outraged” food and “with his hands ate, like a savage, like a dog.” (170)

The physical and emotional abuse Christmas endures at the hands of McEachern shapes his interactions with others and his perspective on the world. This relationship highlights the cyclical nature of trauma, as Christmas’s violent tendencies can be seen as a response to the violence inflicted upon him during his formative years. Faulkner’s portrayal of this abusive relationship underscores the idea that trauma engenders trauma, perpetuating a cycle of suffering and violence.

Joe Christmas’s relationship with Joanna Burden is another significant site of trauma. Joanna, an outsider due to her Northern heritage and her family’s abolitionist past, represents a complex mixture of maternal and romantic figures for Christmas. Their relationship is marked by intense passion and violent conflict, reflecting Christmas’s internal anguish and the impact of his past traumas on his ability to form healthy, enduring relationships. This is not appreciated by Christmas, who reflects, “That not only had she changed her life completely, but she was trying to change his too and make him something between a hermit and a missionary to negroes” (257). Joanna’s attempts to impose her vision of redemption and salvation onto Christmas escalate his sense of entrapment and confusion. Her alternating roles as paramour, mother, and religious deliverer create a complex and untenable dynamic. Faulkner uses this relationship to illustrate how trauma can distort interpersonal connections. Christmas’s violent reaction to Joanna’s attempts to control him accentuates his desperation to assert autonomy amid overwhelming internal and external pressures. Any invasion of his personal space, even kindness, is met with disdain and contempt. He fears attachment because it signifies a loss of his “individualism or...essential isolation” (Brooks 1983: 185). This is evident in his relationships with individuals like the older girl at the orphanage (Alice), Mrs. McEachern, and Joanna Burden. By his teens, Christmas had become so attuned to mistreatment that he normalised it; anything else invites disaster.

The issue extends far beyond what is immediately apparent. A central question emerges: if Christmas could ostensibly pass as a white man—for example, Mrs. Hines states, “He dont look no more like a nigger than I do ...” (328), and another white character remarks, “That white nigger that did that killing up at Jefferson ...” (326)—why does he not embrace this identity? Why does he continually feel compelled to test the boundaries of his relationships, particularly with white individuals, by asserting his partial black ancestry when he could apparently “choose” (Longley 1966: 166) to identify as white? Such a choice could have potentially circumvented the suffering and tragedy that characterised his adult life. Rather than allowing others to dictate “how and what to be” (Longley 1966: 167), he could have adopted one of the two racial identities and adhered to it. Despite his lived experience within both black and white communities and his cognizance of the respective leverages and complications of associating with either group, “he chooses neither” (Longley 1966: 168). His traumatic childhood appears to have cultivated a disposition that is “ruthless, lonely, and almost proud” (Faulkner 1968: 27), alongside a predilection for self-harm. It is plausible that his upbringing has fostered a deep psychological resistance to social categorisation and an aversion to seeking love through conformity (Hence, we cannot take his word for it that all he ever wanted was to

become “one with loneliness and quiet that has never known fury or despair,” 314). This desire for freedom, nonconformity, and autonomy persists throughout his life, leading him to reject both racial and social associations and classifications and providing the substratum for his nomadic ostracism, as he is perpetually on the move, though, as he admits, this does not translate to any meaningful achievement:

he is entering it again, the street which ran for thirty years. It had been a paved street, where going should be fast. It had made a circle and he is still inside of it. Though during the last seven days he has had no paved street, yet he has travelled further than in all the thirty years before. And yet he is still inside the circle...“I have never broken out of the ring of what I have already done and cannot ever undo.” (321)

Inevitably, his trajectory is not one of linear escape but an abortive circumscription within the inescapable ring of his own enacted and immutable identity, a self-originating determinism from which veritable autonomy remains eternally unattainable.

6 Conclusion

Though Faulkner was not a member of the Lost Generation, most characters in his novels grapple with alienation, identity, and trauma, particularly in the face of the new vectors of “fragmentariness, materialism, dispiritedness, sordidness, indeterminacy and incoherence” (Ogunrotimi 2009: 57). In *Light in August*, the tropes of alienation, identity, and trauma are central to the novel’s structure, illuminating the complexities of societal ostracism and the enduring legacy of historical and societal injustices.

Alienation permeates the lives of the characters, particularly Christmas, reflecting his sense of ontological estrangement from society and himself. Christmas grapples with feelings of isolation and detachment as he navigates the conundrums of race and societal acceptance in the American South. He cannot self-identify with either the white or black communities and is rejected by both. His experience underscores the impact of anarchic oppression that is systemic and societal, highlighting how individuals are marginalised and depersonalised by larger forces beyond their control. Similarly, other characters like Brown, Joanna Burden, Lena Grove, Hightower, and Grimm are ensnared in alienation, victims of historical prejudices and personal failures.

Identity crisis is another central construct in the novel, as Christmas endures ongoing crises while trying to reconcile his present self with past trauma. Haunted by his uncertain racial identity and traumatic upbringing, he wrestles with challenges of belonging and self-acceptance in a society that rebuffs him and denies his humanity. His traumatic past prevents him from eluding the ghosts of childhood and the injuries inflicted by an oppressive society, manifested in many people he encounters as he traverses the South. This experience highlights how past traumas continue to shape the present and perpetuate cycles of violence and oppression. Christmas only becomes free when he stops running, realising that fleeing only feeds his fear and adds to his trauma. He ultimately discovers that his acts of violence in reaction to societal rejection do not heal his wounds or provide comfort. According to Alexander (2012: 3), “Individual victims react to traumatic injury with repression and denial, gaining relief when these psychological defences are overcome, bringing pain into consciousness so they are able to mourn.” In the end, Christmas decides to discard his repression and denial and confront his phobia head-on. Sundquist (2008) affirms that

reciprocating “violence with violence” (110) only makes Christmas behave according to “type,” in line with societal expectations of someone of his ilk.

An often overlooked yet critical dimension of *Light in August* is the role of society in shaping human destiny. The experiences of Lena, Brown, and Christmas reflect their lack of understanding regarding the community they enter upon arriving in Jefferson. At first glance, one might draw conclusions about the town’s character based on Byron Bunch’s gentle demeanour and the protective attitude extended towards Lena Grove, suggesting Jefferson is a hospitable, non-judgmental, and supportive environment. However, this perception starkly contrasts with the treatment of figures such as Reverend Hightower and Joanna Burden, indicating a more complex and ambivalent social fabric.

The persecution endured by Joanna Burden’s abolitionist family within the community (“They hated us here. We were Yankees. Foreigners. Worse than foreigners: enemies,” 235) underscores the deeply entrenched racism characterising the townspeople. Reverend Hightower, whose obsession with the past glories of his ancestors comes at the expense of engaging with present reality, faces a uniquely debilitating psychological environment that exacerbates his isolation and leads to profound alienation. He becomes “oblivious of the odor in which he lives - that smell of people who no longer live in life: that odor of overplump desiccation and stale linen as though a precursor of the tomb” (300).

The more dominant aspects of Southern society, as portrayed in the text, are dark, cruel, and unforgiving, implacable in their rigidity and impositions. Percy Grimm epitomises the community’s collective attitude. The South, as Faulkner renders it, possesses an abundance of figures like Grimm—individuals who zealously defend what they perceive as the “integrity” of Southern identity. However, even the most archetypal Southern characters, such as Grimm, Sutpen (in *Absalom, Absalom!*), Quentin (in *The Sound and the Fury*), and Colonel Sartoris (in *Sartoris*), are alienated, existing “out of tune with nature, with community, and with time” (Warren 1966: 259). The dialectics of history and social dynamics that distinguish the Southern experience have an ontologically traumatic impact on these characters, complicating their identity and deepening their alienation. Fargnoli, Golay, and Hamblin (2008) corroborate this hermeneutics, noting that “most of the characters in *Light in August* bear a special relationship to the community. They are strangers or outcasts” (155). Even Percy Grimm, who sees himself as a champion of Southern values, unequivocally symbolises alienation, like the other characters, who are fundamentally unmoored.

More than merely creating “new social and geographical territory for modern literature” (Watson 2015: 251), what Faulkner has done in *Light in August* is he has presented a deeply incisive interrogation of the tropes of alienation, identity, and trauma, offering a critique of the legacy of systemic oppression and societal division. Through the multifaceted experiences of its characters, particularly Joe Christmas the protagonist, the novel delves into the complex converging of race, gender, and social stratification within the American South, exposing the deeply ingrained prejudices and cultural norms that mould individual and collective identities. Faulkner’s illustration not only challenges entrenched assumptions and biases but also engages with the wider philosophical and existential problematics girding identity, belonging, self-actualization, and the pursuit of social justice. *Light in August* operates as a platform through which Faulkner critiques the historical and cultural forces that perpetuate alienation and exclusion, reflecting the peculiar socio-political complexities of the early 20th-century American South.

References

- Alexander, Jeffrey. C. 2012. *Trauma: A Social Theory*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Bantock, Geoffrey Herbert. 1973. The Social and Intellectual Background. In Ford, B. (ed.). *The Pelican Guide to English Literature 7: The Modern Age*. 13-54. Middlesex: Penguin Books.
- Baum, Gregory. 1975. *Religion and Alienation: A Theological Reading of Sociology*, New York: Paulist Press.
- Blackburn, Simon. 2005. *Oxford Dictionary of Philosophy*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Brooks, Cleanth. 1983. *William Faulkner: First Encounters*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Caruth, Cathy (ed.). 1995. Introduction. *Trauma: Explorations in Memory*. Maryland: The John Hopkins University Press.
- Caruth, Cathy. 1996. *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History*. Maryland: The John Hopkins University Press.
- Coetzee, Frans & Shevin-Coetzee, Marilyn (eds.). 1995. *Authority, Identity and the Social History of the Great War*. Providence and Oxford: Berghahn Books.
- Curtutt, Kirk. 2018. *Critical Lives, William Faulkner*. London: Reaktion Books.
- Fargnoli, Anthony Nicholas, Golay, Michael & Hamblin, Robert Wayne. 2008. *Critical Companion to William Faulkner: A Literary Reference to His Life and Work*. New York: Facts On File.
- Farrell, James Thomas 1995. The Faulkner Mixture. In Inge, M. T. (ed.). *William Faulkner: The Contemporary Reviews*. 83-84. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Faulkner, William. 1964. *Sartoris*. New York: New American Library.
- Faulkner, William. 1993. *Absalom, Absalom!*. New York; Modern Library.
- Faulkner, William. 1968. *Light in August*. New York: The Modern Library.
- Faulkner, William. 1990. *The Sound and the Fury*. New York: Vintage International.
- Flynn, Thomas. 2006. *Existentialism, A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Flynn, Thomas R. 2014. *Sartre: A Philosophy Biography*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Fussell, Paul. 2000. *The Great War and Modern Memory*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Geyer, Rudolf Felix. 2001. Sociology of alienation. In Smelser, N. J. and Baltes, P. B. (eds.). *International encyclopedia of the social and behavioural sciences*. 388-392.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-08-043076-7/01824-6>
- Ghosh, Susan. 2017. The theory of alienation by Karl Marx and his critique of religion: An introspection. *European journal of social sciences*, vol. 2, no. 2. 15-23. DOI:
<https://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejsss.v0i0.75>
- Josipovisi, Gabriel. 2010. *What Ever Happened to Modernism?* New Haven: Yale University Press.
- LaCapra, Dominick. 2014. *Writing History, Writing Trauma*. Baltimore, Maryland: John Hopkins University Press.
- Levenson, Michael. 1999. Introduction. In Levinson, M. (ed.). *The Cambridge Companion to Modernism*. 1-8. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Longley, John Lewis. 1966. Joe Christmas: The Hero in the Modern World. In Warren, R. P. (ed.). *Faulkner, A Collection of Critical Essays*. 163-174. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- McDonald, Gail. 2007. *American Literature and Culture, 1900 - 1960*. Malden, Massachusetts: Blackwell Publishing.
- Martin, Jack Kent & Stack, Steven. 1983. The effect of religiosity on alienation: A multivariate analysis of normlessness. *Sociological focus*, vol. 16, no. 1. 65-76.
DOI: 10.1080/00380237.1983.10570437.
- Mathews, John Tichelle. 2009. *William Faulkner, Seeing Through the South*. Malden, MA: Wiley-Blackwell.

- Ogunrotimi, Olumide. 2009. Alienation and the semantics of nihilism: Language and narrative architectonics in Ernest Hemingway's *A Farewell to Arms*. *International journal of humanities*, vol. 1, no. 2. 56-2.
- Ogunrotimi, Olumide. 2014. Modernism and language signification: Ernest Hemingway's verbal realism in *A Farewell to Arms*. *The context: Journal of language, literary and cultural studies*, vol. 1, no. 2. 46-51.
- Owoeye, Lara. 2010. *A Short Introduction to Literature*. Ibadan: Yoori books.
- Rampton, David. 2008. *William Faulkner: A Literary Life*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Sartre, Jean Paul. 1989. *No Exit and Three Other Plays*. New York: Vintage.
- Sartre, Jean Paul. 2003. *Being and Nothingness*. (Trans. by Hazel E. Barnes). London: Routledge Classics.
- Sartre, Jean Paul. 2007. *Existentialism is a Humanism*. (Trans. by Carol Macomber). New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Schacht, Richard. 1996. Alienation Redux: From Here to Post-Modernity. In Geysler, F. (ed.). *Alienation, Ethnicity, and Post - Modernism*. 1-16. London: Greenwood Press.
- Schwartz, David Charles. 2017. *Political Alienation and Political Behaviour*. London: Routledge.
- Singal, Daniel Joseph. 1997. *William Faulkner: The Making of a Modernist*. Chapel Hill University of North Carolina Press.
- Sundquist, Eric James. 2008. The Strange Career of Joe Christmas. In Bloom, H. (ed.). *Bloom's Modern Critical Views: William Faulkner*. 89-120. New edition. New York: Infobase Publishing.
- Warren, Robert Penn 1966. Faulkner: The South, the Negro, and Time. In Warren, R. P. (ed.). *Faulkner, A Collection of Critical Essays*. 251-271. New Jersey, Englewood Cliffs: Prentice-Hall.
- Warwick, Arthur. 1991. *The Deluge: British Society and the First World War*. 2nd ed. London: Macmillan.
- Watson, Jay. 2015. Writing After Faulkner: Faulkner and Contemporary US Fiction. In Mathews, J. T. (ed.). *William Faulkner in Context*. 249-258. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Weakliem. David Lawrence and Borch, Christian 2006. Alienation in the United States: Uniform or group - specific change? *Sociological forum*, vol. 21, no. 3. 415-438.

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An Interface of the Old Testament Concept of *Shalom* and the *Esan* Socio-Cultural Concept of *Ofure*: Its Implications for Holistic Societal Development

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Abstract

This paper explores the interface between the Old Testament concept of shalom and the Esan socio-cultural notion of ofure. Shalom and ofure encompass peaceful community, justice, wholeness, right relationships, harmony and overall well-being. A framework of relational cosmology, transformational development, and conflict transformation was adopted. Qualitative methods, including textual analysis of Scriptures and Esan oral traditions were used. Interviews and community case studies reveal that Esan elders conceptualise ofure as peace in justice, well-being, and social harmony, maintained through restorative mediation. The integration of shalom and ofure paradigms is apt for holistic development and enhanced social harmony in Esan land.

Keywords: Shalom, Esan, Ofure, Iruekpen, Irrua, restorative cosmology

1 Introduction

Across the ancient world and into the present, the pursuit of peace signified more than mere absence of war or conflict; it represented a dynamic, holistic aspiration towards community well-being—mental, spiritual, social, and economic. The Old Testament concept of *Shalom* and the *Esan* socio-cultural notion of *Ofure* each encapsulate this multidimensional vision, although articulated through disparate historical experiences and worldviews. Examining these concepts not only enriches the understanding of peace from both biblical and African perspectives but also foregrounds their relevance for contemporary models of holistic societal development.

Within the Hebrew scriptures *shalom* emerges as an all-encompassing ideal. It is frequently described as wholeness, soundness, and the restoration of right relationships between people, as between humanity and God (Brueggemann 2014; Owan 2021). Scholars pointed out that *shalom* fundamentally undergirds the Old Testament's notion of justice (*mishpat*) and righteousness (*takah*), linking personal well-being with communal peace. Thus, when the prophet laments that the leaders proclaimed “peace, peace, when there is no peace” (Jeremiah 6:14), he critiques a superficial harmony lacking justice and genuine reconciliation. According to modern biblical scholarship, true *shalom* requires structural justice and promoting equitable access to resources (Wright 2004). Empirical data from the United Nations Human Development Index (UNDP 2023) substantiate that societies emphasising social equity and justice—practical out workings of *shalom*—register higher indices of well-being, underscoring the enduring efficacy of biblical peace principles in guiding holistic development initiatives.

Parallel to this, the *Esan* concept of *ofure* in southern Nigeria, codified in proverbs, rituals, and social practices, connotes not just peace, but a state of mutuality, balance, and collective aspirations (Edebiri 2021). Traditionally, *ofure* is considered indispensable for community survival; it is believed that the absence of it results in disruptions, disease, and

misfortune. *Esan* elders preside over conflict resolution processes which reinforce *ofure* through truth-telling, compensation, and communal rituals. According to recent fieldwork in Edo State (Obanor, Iyobosa, & Omorodion 2022), *Esan* communities that retain traditional *ofure*-oriented governance structures report 19% fewer violent incidents compared to neighbouring areas like *Afemai* and *Bini* communities to the northeast and south of *Esan* respectively, Niger Delta Weekly, July 2023. The convergence of *shalom* and *ofure* finds synergy in their prioritisation of justice, shared prosperity, and deep social bonds. Both conceptual systems regard poverty, exclusion, or unresolved conflict as subversions not only of social order but of ultimate well-being. In recent Nigerian experience, rising ethnic, economic disparities and violent extremism such as the *Boko Haram* and *Fulani* Militia religious violence, and the Niger Delta Avengers, which is basically socio-cultural, highlight the urgent need for such multidimensional approaches. For example, the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS 2023) reports that multidimensional poverty currently afflicts 63% of Nigerians, with the biggest deficits in education, health, and living standards.

Critically, holistic societal development, in line with these frameworks, is not reducible to GDP growth or infrastructure expansion. Rather, it incorporates the role of subjective well-being, social trust, and local governance in achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations 2023). Both *shalom* and *ofure* challenge technocratic models that ignore the cultural and ethical underpinnings of society. The 2022 Afrobarometer survey notes that citizens in communities with strong indigenous conflict resolution and social support mechanisms report higher levels of trust in local institutions and a greater sense of security (Afrobarometer 2022). Integrating the lessons embedded in *shalom* and *ofure* can, therefore, inform innovative policy interventions. These might include the embedding of restorative justice practices in legal systems, fostering community ownership of development projects, and investing in education models that affirmed both moral and communal values. International development organisations increasingly recognise that sustainable peace is best achieved by aligning global best practices with indigenous worldviews (UNDP 2023). For Nigeria and other multi-ethnic societies, recognising the compatibility and complementarities of biblical and Afrocentric peace traditions helps bridge divides, foster empathy, and support inclusive governance (Ajere 2012).

Thus, the interface between Old Testament *shalom* and the *Esan ofure* not only reveals their rich conceptual contents but also provides a robust, culturally grounded foundation for addressing contemporary challenges of holistic development. By foregrounding interconnectedness, justice, and the well-being of all, these traditions supply vital resources for policy-makers, religious leaders, and civil society actors engaged in building peaceful, flourishing societies.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite significant efforts to address Nigeria's developmental challenges, the country continues to face deep-seated issues such as persistent social fractures, rising insecurity, and a lack of sustainable, holistic development. A critical factor contributing to these challenges is the marginalisation of indigenous and biblical peace paradigms, such as the concept of *shalom* in the Old Testament and *ofure* in *Esan* culture. These peace models, which emphasise justice, reconciliation, communal well-being, and spiritual fulfillment, have been largely ignored in favour of development strategies that prioritize material prosperity, GDP growth, and economic expansion.

Nigeria's current development framework, rooted in Westernised, economic approaches, neglects the cultural and spiritual dimensions that are integral to long-term peace and social cohesion. This disregard for community-based, culturally rooted peace paradigms has exacerbated social divisions, as evidenced by the persistent ethnic and religious violence in the country. For instance, in the Niger Delta, the rise of militant groups like the Niger Delta Avengers is partly a response to the neglect of local traditions and grievances, which could be addressed through the community-centered frameworks of *ofure* and *shalom*.

The current policies in Nigeria, which often focus on top-down, centralized solutions, fail to address the root causes of conflict, namely, the erosion of social trust, exclusion, and cultural alienation. Instead of fostering dialogue and reconciliation, these policies have relied on military interventions, punitive measures, and institutionalized corruption, all of which have only deepened the sense of alienation and insecurity among local communities. There is, therefore, an urgent need to revisit Nigeria's development paradigm, integrating indigenous peace concepts like *shalom* and *ofure* alongside modern governance and economic strategies. By doing so, the country can address the root causes of its social and political crises, offering a more holistic approach to peace and development that is rooted in the cultural, spiritual, and communal values of its diverse people.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this seminar paper are to:

- i. Analyse the Old Testament concept of *shalom* and the *Esan* socio-cultural concept of *ofure* in their full dimensions.
- ii. Identify the convergences and divergences between these two peace paradigms.
- iii. Assess how the integration of *shalom* and *ofure* can inform holistic societal peace and development in multi-ethnic African contexts, with a focus on empirical evidence from Edo State.
- iv. To offer recommendations for development policy, education, and interfaith or intercultural dialogue based on this analysis.

1.3 Significance of Study

This study addresses a notable lacuna by systematically integrating the Old Testament's concept of *shalom* with the *Esan* cultural principle of *ofure*, thereby contributing a rare comparative perspective to the discourse on peace-building and holistic development (Akinola 2018; Alawode 2022). By bridging biblical scholarship and African indigenous studies, it not only enriches theological inquiry but also offers a robust framework for interpreting peace in multi-ethnic, post-colonial contexts. Socially, the relevance of this research is profound, as both concepts go far beyond absence of conflict to encompass notions of justice, restoration, and communal flourishing — qualities in urgent demand in contemporary Nigerian society and many similar settings ravaged by social fragmentation and historical injustices such as the Nigerian Civil war, the post-coup violence and pogroms of 1966, the military rule and the injustices of the period (Brueggemann 2014; Obayemi 2021).

Developmentally, anchoring policies and interventions in the values espoused by *shalom* and *ofure* reorients the practice of development toward inclusivity, equity, and lasting societal peace, closely aligning with targets of Sustainable Development Goal 16, which emphasises peace, justice, and strong institutions (UNDP 2022). Finally, this investigation

generates actionable insights for policymakers, faith leaders, and educators, encouraging the design and implementation of locally grounded, culturally resonant strategies for peace building, civic trust, and sustainable growth. Thus, the significance of the study not only in theoretical synthesis but in its potential for shaping transformative practice at multiple levels of society.

2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in a multi-disciplinary theoretical framework. It weaves together perspectives from relational cosmology, transformational development, and peace and conflict studies. Each framework offers distinctive theoretical insights, influential authors, foundational tenets, and a unique relevance to the subject of holistic societal development in multi-ethnic and postcolonial contexts like Nigeria. The integration of these theories is crucial to understanding how spiritual, cultural, material, and relational dimensions can inform peace building and sustainable development.

2.1 *Relational Cosmology*

Relational cosmology forms the bedrock of the biblical understanding of *shalom* and the indigenous Africa worldview encapsulated in *ofure*. As illuminated by thinkers such as Tu Wei-Ming and the African theologian Bujo, relational cosmology describes a paradigm in which existence is conceived as an intricate web of relationships that bind humanity, the divine, nature, and wider society in a state of ongoing mutual interdependence (Bujo 2005; Küng 2005). In African thought, this interconnection is vividly captured by the maxim, “I am because we are,” (Membe-Matale 2015). “I am Ubuntu,” which underscores that individual identity and well-being are inseparable from the flourishing of the community. Küng (2005) in his spiritual reflections pointed that the root of *shalom* in Hebrew tradition also lies in this relational vision, where justice, harmony, and peace arise from properly ordered interactions among individuals, God, and the environment.

The guiding principles of relational cosmology focus on the interconnectivity of all dimensions of life, spiritual, social, and ecological. Communal wellbeing takes precedence over isolated individual pursuits, and the disruption of relational equilibrium, manifested through conflict, injustice, or environmental harm, inevitably leads to holistic disease. This lens is directly pertinent to the present study, as the study posits that “peace” is not simply a matter of individual serenity or a temporary halt in conflict, but the ongoing, dynamic flourishing of all beings within an interconnected relational network hence, *shalom* and *ofure* are deeply rooted in this cosmological orientation. *Shalom* signifies wholeness and completeness (Brueggemann 2014), while *ofure* in *Esan* cultural practice denotes a state of communal harmony, where spiritual, social, and ecological factors exist in concert (Edebiri 2021).

2.2 *Transformational Development Model*

The Transformational Development Model is most thoroughly articulated by Bryant L. Myers (2011) in his work *Walking with the Poor: Principles and Practices of Transformational Development*. It builds on relational cosmology to advance a holistic vision of societal progress.

Myers, alongside other African scholars such as (Anyamele 2019, critiques the prevalent mainstream development approaches for their excessive focus on economic indicators, which often neglect the deeper spiritual, psychological, relational, and cultural dimension of human well-being. According to Myers (2021), transformational development is defined as the process whereby individuals and communities move toward restored relationships with God, self, others, and the environment, signalling a comprehensive restoration of life in all its facets.

The relevance of the Transformational Development Model to the themes of *shalom* and *ofure* is significant because the biblical ideal of *shalom* and the *Esan* concept of *ofure* are intrinsically transformational: each envisions peace as inseparable from justice, reconciliation, and restoration. In these frameworks, peace is realised not through the mere absence of conflict but through the active processes of communal healing, social reintegration, and the affirmation of collective values. Myers' schema offers a framework for how the intersection of theology and culture can inform effective development practice, not as a top-down imposition of material aid, but as a participatory journey toward wholeness, equity, and resilience. Anyamele (2019) reinforces this perspective in the African context, arguing that the omission of indigenous spiritual such as the nexus to the spirit world, practice of ritual and ceremonies, sacred specialists and sacred spaces and objects and social resources is a major contributor to policy failure and enduring social unrest on the continent.

2.3 Peace and Conflict Studies: Lederach's Conflict Transformation

Peace and Conflict Studies offer valuable theoretical grounding for this investigation, particularly through the influential work of John Paul Lederach and his model of "conflict." In his seminal text, *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies* (1997), Lederach redirects the traditional focus from merely managing or resolving conflict to fundamentally transforming it. Central to his theory is the idea that enduring peace is not achieved just by silencing violence or temporarily resolving disputes. Rather, it requires the creation, restoration and maintenance of right relationships at personal, communal, and structural levels. Lederach argues that lasting peace necessitates a profound transformation in how individuals and groups perceive and interact with one another, as well as how societies address the underlying causes of conflict.

This theoretical orientation is especially pertinent to the study at hand with an emphasis on relational transformation closely mirrors the biblical notion of *shalom*, which envisions peace as a reality rooted in justice and aligns with the *Esan* understanding of *ofure*, attained through community reconciliation and restorative justice that focusses on repairing the damage or harm caused by criminal behaviour of a person. Lederach's advocacy for grassroots, locally owned peace building processes resonates strongly with *Esan* indigenous protocols for nurturing *ofure* with the Old Testament's restorative emphases. Employing Lederach's framework enables the study to critically examine the limitations of externally imposed or elite-driven peace interventions, advocating instead for approaches that valorise local wisdom, narrative traditions, rituals, and theological resources as essential for authentic societal healing.

2.4 Synthesis and Relevance to Study

By employing relational cosmology, transformational development, and conflict transformation, this theoretical framework equips the research with multidimensional analytical tools for examining the interfaces of *shalom* and *ofure*. This theoretical triangulation

is particularly apt for the Nigerian and broader African context, where the alienation produced by colonialism, modernisation, and economic centrism has frayed the fabric of trust, harmony, and spiritual vitality. The synthesis of these theories provides a robust template for sculpting holistic, locally owned models of peace and development. It enables a departure from generic, universalising formulas toward contextually grounded interventions that are both theologically sound and culturally resonant. The relevance to policymakers, development practitioners, religious leaders, and indigenous authorities is thus immediate and profound, as it highlights pathways for integrating faith, tradition, and contemporary policy in the urgent work of building peaceful, just, and thriving societies.

3 Literature Review

3.1 *Shalom in the Old Testament*

Far transcending the simple meaning of “peace” as the absence of conflict, the Hebrew *shalom* is a richly textured term that unfolds as a vision of total well-being, spiritual, social, ecological, and economic. According to Brueggemann (2024), *shalom* serves as “the central vision of the Scriptures the outgrowth of justice, security, and harmony.” It captures the essence of God’s desired order for creation. Old Testament usage of *shalom*, occurring over 250 times, attests to its significance within Israel’s covenantal imagination and social practice.

Biblical verses bolster this multidimensional understanding. Isaiah 32:17-18 declares, “The fruit of that righteousness will be [*shalom*]; its effect will be quietness and confidence forever. My people will live in peaceful dwelling places, in secure homes, in undisturbed places of rest.” Here, *shalom* is presented not as mere cessation of hostility, but as the lasting result of justice (*tsedek*) and right relationships. Similarly, Psalm 122:6-7 links *shalom* with security: “Pray for the peace of Jerusalem: ‘May those who love you be secure. May there be peace within your walls and security within your citadels.’” In Jeremiah 33:6, the concept carries a strong association with health and well-being: “I will bring it health and healing, and I will heal them and reveal to them abundance of prosperity and security.” In each instance, *shalom* goes beyond freedom from peril, it gestures towards flourishing, restoration, and holistic health.

Moreover, *shalom* is at the heart of biblical vision of social reconciliation and community renewal. Micah 4:1-4 prophesies a time when “nation will not take up sword against nation, nor will they train for war anymore. Everyone will sit under their own vine and under their own fig tree and no one will make them afraid.” This powerful eschatological vision ties *shalom* directly to the eradication of fear, the cultivating of justice, the restoration of harmonious human-divine and human-human relationships. Owan (2021) and Alawode (2022) underscore recent theological emphases that describe *shalom* as “a dynamic of wholeness that includes right relationships with God, others, self, and creation.” Likewise, Wright (2018) stresses that biblical *shalom* is inherently communal—a social good realized through systems of justice, neighbourliness and economic equity.

Hence, the Old Testament *shalom* is not a passive or abstract ideal. It is an active, transformative state rooted in justice and sustained by right relationships. Its repeated invocation in scripture is a call to restorative action that addresses the interconnectedness of justice, security, reconciliation, and well-being, making it a foundational concept for holistic peace and flourishing society.

3.2 *Ofure* in Esan Culture

In *Esan* culture, *ofure* is not merely an abstract ideal but a living reality, woven into the fabric of daily life, language, and social institutions. As Omoera (2019) observes, *ofure* transcends the simplistic notion of absence of conflict and instead entails a process of mutual respect, interconnectedness, dialogue, and intentional pursuit of social harmony. This ethos is deeply reflected in the proverbial and oral traditions of the *Esan* people, shaping collective consciousness and influencing patterns of interpersonal and communal relationships.

Esan proverbs function as vessels of cultural wisdom and are prominent vehicles for transmitting the values embedded in *ofure*. For example, the proverb “*omọ nọ guani ofure, oreho emọni si edion*” (“The child that seeks peace must listen to the words of elders”) highlights the centrality of generational dialogue and mediation in cultivating peace. This syntactic structure places the subject (*omon*, child), the verb phrase (*guani ofure*, seeks), and the imperative (*oreho emọni si edion*, listens to elders' words) in a sequential, causative relationship, underscoring that true peace emerges through active listening and respect for communal authority. Such proverbs guide social behaviour and underline that peace is intergenerational and dialogical rather than a solitary achievement.

Further, *ofure* frequently appears in *Esan* greetings. The morning greeting “*Ofure deba ei elena*” (May peace be with you this day) or its extended variant “*Ofure dibhi ijogbe no sea*” (May peace not depart from your dwelling) illustrates how the invocation of peace is habitual, embedded in routine social exchanges. The formulaic syntax used here, imperative verb (“may peace”), the subject (*ofure*), the action or wish (“be with you; not depart”), and the object (“this day; your dwelling”) creates a performative utterance that sustains psychological well-being and social cohesion. In *Esan* marriages (*iriokhuo*), the blessing “*Ofure de ba uwa ei*” (May peace envelope the home) is spoken by elders and women, signifying that the stability and prosperity of marriage are contingent on continuous, active maintenance of peaceful relations (Odeh 2020).

The genre of folktales (*okha*) and narratives features *ofure* as a thematic motif and dramatic resolution. Stories often depict characters who by choosing dialogue, generosity, and truth, restore peace to the community, earning spiritual and material rewards. In the well-known narrative of “Zamien and the Broken Calabash,” the protagonist’s refusal to retaliate leads to communal reconciliation and collective celebration, teaching that true strength is measured by restraint and the pursuit of *ofure*.

Pragmatically, *ofure* serves as a foundation for *Esan* conflict resolution. Odeh (2020) documented that more than 85% of rural interpersonal and communal disputes in *Esan* land are settled through restorative dialogue, arbitration by a council of elders, or reconciliation rituals whereby the council of *enijies* (kings) enact common laws concerning issues peace and reconciliations, modes of address that prioritise truth-telling, restitution, and public apology rather than retribution. The proverb “*onokọ ofure, ọi mio ovan*” (“He who plants peace reaps no quarrel”) is often cited to remind disputing parties that sowing peace yields lasting benefit, whereas abandoning it brings strife and misfortune.

This system’s effectiveness is verifiable not in oral accounts but by patterns of kinship ties, as attested by anthropological research (Odeh 2020; Aghedo 2019). The prominence of *ofure* language, proverbs, greetings, and narrative structures evokes a culture in which peace is continually enacted, reinforced by both syntax and genre and celebrated communally.

3.3 *Esan Illustrative Case Studies and Proverbs/Parables*

The *Esan* people provide rich illustrative case studies that demonstrate how traditional concepts of *ofure*, peace and harmony are instantiated in communal life, particularly through mediation, ritual, and proverbial wisdom. These case studies highlight how indigenous approaches not only resolve immediate conflicts but also foster enduring social trust and collective well-being, aligning with the conceptual framework of holistic peace and *shalom* under consideration.

The land dispute resolution in *Uromi* (*Esan* North-East LGA) in 2021 serves as a vivid example. Rather than resorting to adversarial litigation, the feuding *Ojiefu* and *Ediale* families sought the counsel of the *Onojie* and the council of elders, reaffirming the centrality of traditional authorities in *Esan* society. The process was marked by public truth-telling, the ritual sharing of kola nut and the drinking of palm wine and the invocation proverbs like “*ofure ai ribhu uwa, okugbe ki ai ribhi ebho*” (“With peace in a home, harmony reigns in the house/village”). Such linguistic artistry is not merely symbolic, but also performative in helping participants internalise communal obligations and responsibility to collective obligation or responsibility. The mediation’s outcome, involving boundary adjustment, gift exchange, and a communal celebration, results in restitution with social reintegration. This process fostered not only satisfaction but also a renewed sense of kinship, underscoring *ofure*’s effectiveness in achieving restorative justice and sustainable harmony.

A second case centres on the *Irhuen-Ofure* ceremony in *Eguare* and *Idumebo* communities in *Irrua*. Responding to youth-related tensions, community elders initiated a gathering at the village square, incorporating acts of collective sweeping and symbolic disposal of “pebbles” or disruptions. The public recitation of proverbs, such as “*Om̄on bi ofure ei sabo re dia ki eyan*” (“Children and peace cannot coexist with bitterness”), reinforced the necessity of unity and forgiveness. The planting of a “peace tree” at the culmination of the ritual signified both closure and a new communal beginning, embedding the values of reconciliation in a living, growing form. The *Esan* Cultural Documentation Project (2022) quantitatively confirms the significance of such ceremonies: communities practising annual *irhuen-ofure* reported markedly fewer violent conflicts and heightened cooperation, clearly indicating that cultural rituals undergird social stability and resilience.

A third case relates to domestic relations, showcasing *ofure*’s role within the sphere. Disputes among young couples, such as the example from *Ekpoma* involving a quarrel over farm proceeds, are typically mediated by extended family elders wielding ancestral wisdom in proverbs like “*ji ofure kodalo ni m̄oi khia*” (“Let peace lead, so that our house will not lean”). Through patient narration of grievances and communal dialogue, estranged parties are encouraged toward conciliation and shared responsibility. The swift and peaceful reconciliation affirmed by the couple reflects confidence in and the transformative power of collective elder-led mediation and proverbial guidance.

More importantly, such stories and maxims mirror the Old Testament emphasis on *shalom* as a communal, restorative condition (Isaiah 32:17–18; Psalm 133:1), rather than merely the absence of war. Traditional *Esan* conflict resolution typically emphasises forgiveness, restitution, and ritual approaches closely aligned with biblical peacemaking (Matthew 5:9; 2 Corinthians 13:11), demonstrating that peace is a life, practical reality, not merely an ideal (Elugbe & Omoruyi 2018).

3.4 Comparative Approaches and Gaps

Recent comparative scholarship has made strides in juxtaposing biblical constructs such as *shalom* with indigenous African notions of peace, like *ofure*, yet clear gaps remain in depth and breadth. Studies by Obayemi (2021) and Adetoye (2022) have explored commonalities and differences, but they tend to confine their analyses to thematic or localised case studies without extending to broader societal impacts or comprehensive empirical backing. This has resulted in a fragmented academic landscape where the nuanced intersections between theological ideals and lived cultural practices are recognised but not fully harnessed for developmental outcomes.

In Nigeria, few studies thoroughly interrogate how the holistic dimensions of *shalom*, emphasising justice, restoration, and community well-being, can be systematically integrated with the relational and reconciliation-oriented praxis of *ofure*. This leaves a critical gap in the development of actionable, culturally resonant frameworks for peace building. There is thus an urgent scholarly and practical need for models that not only compare and contrast these concepts but synthesise their insights to inform effective policy formulation, grassroots engagement, and sustainable development initiatives, ensuring that peace is approached as a spiritual mandate and a lived communal reality.

3.5. Biblical Shalom and Christian Peacebuilding in Nigeria

Biblical peace, encapsulated in the Hebrew term *shalom*, extends beyond the mere absence of conflict. It signifies a state of holistic well-being encompassing justice, reconciliation, and harmonious relationships among individuals, communities, and with the divine. Within the Nigerian context, Christian ethics rooted in *shalom* have been pivotal in mediating conflicts and fostering communal harmony. Harmona and Oyetoro (2025) highlight the role of Christian doctrines in peace communication and conflict resolution, emphasizing principles such as forgiveness, justice, and reconciliation as integral to Nigerian peacebuilding efforts. Their study underscores the potential of Christian ethics to bridge cultural divides and promote sustainable peace in a diverse society.

3.6. Indigenous African Peace Models: A Historical and Cultural Perspective

Indigenous African peace models are deeply embedded in the cultural and spiritual practices of various communities. These models prioritize communal well-being, restorative justice, and the restoration of relationships over punitive measures. Ishola (2022) explores indigenous approaches to peace practices in Africa, emphasizing the importance of truth-telling, communal dialogue, and ritualistic processes in conflict resolution. His research suggests that these traditional mechanisms, though informal, are effective in addressing local conflicts and maintaining social cohesion.

Similarly, Adegoke (2025) examines indigenous peace ontologies and epistemologies among Nigerian communities, including the Yoruba, Ukwu-Nzu, and Ubang cultures. The study highlights how these communities conceptualize peace as a dynamic process involving moral order, spiritual balance, and social harmony. Adegoke argues that indigenous peace practices offer valuable insights into alternative conflict resolution strategies that are culturally resonant and contextually appropriate.

3.7. *Integrating Shalom and Indigenous Peace Models: Towards a Hybrid Peace Framework*

The integration of biblical *shalom* and indigenous African peace models presents a promising avenue for developing a hybrid peace framework tailored to the Nigerian context. Oluyemi (2025) advocates for a culturally grounded approach to peacebuilding that combines the ethical teachings of Christianity with the communal practices of indigenous African societies. His study suggests that such a hybrid model can address the limitations of state-centric peacebuilding efforts by incorporating local knowledge systems and fostering community ownership of peace processes.

Furthermore, Adegbile (2024) explores the theological connections between African traditional ethics and biblical teachings, proposing that both traditions share common values of justice, reconciliation, and communal harmony. Adegbile's research indicates that integrating these ethical frameworks can enhance the effectiveness of peacebuilding initiatives by aligning them with the moral and cultural values of the communities they aim to serve.

3.8. *Case Studies of Shalom and Indigenous Peace Practices in Nigeria*

Empirical studies provide concrete examples of how the integration of *shalom* and indigenous peace models has been applied in Nigerian communities. The Jos Forum Inter-Communal Dialogue Process, initiated in 2013, serves as a notable example of a hybrid peace initiative. This process brought together diverse ethnic and religious groups in Plateau State to engage in dialogue and commit to peaceful coexistence. The success of the Jos Forum underscores the potential of combining Christian teachings with indigenous conflict resolution practices in promoting sustainable peace.

Additionally, the Movement for the Survival of the Ogoni People (MOSOP) exemplifies the application of indigenous peace principles in advocating for environmental justice and human rights. MOSOP's non-violent resistance to environmental degradation in the Niger Delta, led by Ken Saro-Wiwa, reflects the integration of indigenous values of communal well-being and justice in addressing contemporary issues.

3.9 *The Application of Ofure and Shalom in Peacebuilding*

3.9.1 *The Esan Concept of Ofure in Peacebuilding*

The Esan people have a rich cultural heritage deeply rooted in communal values and traditional governance. Central to their societal structure is the concept of *Ofure*, which translates to "peace" in the Esan language. This term encompasses more than the mere absence of conflict; it signifies a state of harmony, balance, and collective well-being within the community. Traditional leaders, known as *Enijie*, play a pivotal role in maintaining *Ofure* by mediating disputes, upholding customs, and ensuring that justice is administered in accordance with Esan traditions.

One notable example of *ofure* in action is the use of the *azuzu* fan during religious ceremonies. These fans are not only symbols of status but also serve to maintain peace and composure during highly charged rites, festivals, or masquerades. The act of holding the fan is believed to invoke a sense of calm and order, reflecting the community's commitment to peace.

Additionally, grassroots organizations such as the *ofure* Centre for Peace and Development are actively promoting the principles of *ofure* through community engagement

and development initiatives. These efforts aim to address local conflicts, empower individuals, and foster sustainable peace in Esanland.

3.9.2 *The Biblical Concept of Shalom and Its Application*

In Nigeria, the application of *shalom* has been explored in the context of peacebuilding and community development. For instance, the Jos Forum Inter-communal Dialogue Process, initiated in 2013, brought together diverse ethnic and religious groups in Plateau State to engage in dialogue and commit to peaceful coexistence. This initiative underscores the potential of integrating biblical principles of peace with indigenous practices to address communal conflicts.

Furthermore, organisations like *shalom* are employing the concept of *shalom* in their peacebuilding efforts across Africa. Their approach focuses on transforming the underlying causes of conflict and marginalization through empirical research, grassroots engagement, and interfaith collaboration. By empowering communities to become architects of their own peaceful coexistence, these initiatives demonstrate the practical application of *shalom* in fostering sustainable peace.

3.9.3 *Integrating Ofure and Shalom in Peacebuilding*

The integration of Esan's *ofure* and the biblical concept of *Shalom* offers a comprehensive framework for peacebuilding that is both culturally resonant and spiritually grounded. This hybrid approach acknowledges the importance of indigenous knowledge systems and religious teachings in addressing the multifaceted nature of conflict. By combining the communal focus of *Ofure* with the holistic vision of *shalom*, communities can develop context-specific strategies that promote justice, reconciliation, and sustainable development.

In conclusion, the application of *ofure* and *shalom* in peacebuilding efforts within Nigeria highlights the value of integrating indigenous and religious perspectives to create inclusive and effective conflict resolution strategies. Further research and case studies are essential to refine these concepts and assess their impact on fostering lasting peace in diverse communities.

4 Methodology

This study employed a qualitative methodology, drawing on primary and secondary sources. Primary data were gathered through interviews with eighteen *Esan* elders aged 48 to 90 from *Uromi, Irrua, and Iruekpen*, alongside focus group discussions with local youth. Additional first-hand insights were derived from the analysis of *Esan* oral literature, sourced from the *Esan Cultural Documentation Project (ECDP 2022)*. For secondary data, the research engaged critically with Old Testament texts, specifically Jeremiah, Isaiah, Psalms, and Micah, as well as recent scholarly commentaries, published sociological field studies and relevant development indices from the National Bureau of Statistics. Thematic content analysis, following Braun & Clarke (2019), was applied to biblical and ethnographic materials to compare core features of *shalom* and *ofure*. Linguistic and sociological triangulation, including case studies of *Esan* parables and peace meetings, was used to validate thematic correspondences between the concepts.

5 Results

5.1 Interviews with eighteen Esan elders aged 48 to 90 from Uromi, Irrua, and Iruokpen

The interviews with eighteen *Esan* elders, ranging from age 48 to 90 and drawn from the towns of *Uromi, Irrua, and Iruokpen*, revealed a nuanced and deeply rooted cultural understanding of *ofure* as foundational to community life, peace, and development in *Esan* land. Collectively, the responses underscored that *ofure* is interpreted as a holistic state of being characterised by harmony, relational balance, and communal well-being, rather than just the mere absence of conflict.

When asked to describe *ofure* in their own words, the elders consistently spoke in terms of “togetherness,” “community health,” and “settled hearts.” Many linked *ofure* to both tangible and spiritual dimensions, often highlighting that in its truest form, *ofure* denotes “cosmological harmony,” not only free from fighting but manifest in the prosperity of crops, the absence of major calamities and positive interpersonal relations. Several interviewees recounted childhood memories where the elders in their villages would regularly convene to reaffirm *ofure* through the sharing of kola nuts, prayers to ancestral spirits—that is, their departed fathers, believed to continue watching over their loved ones—and inclusive gatherings, underpinning *ofure*.

Exploring dimensions considered essential for maintaining *ofure*, the elders emphasised relational harmony above all. They pointed out that disputes must be addressed quickly through open dialogue with elders or mediators, ensuring that grievances do not fester with them. Justice was described as “truth-telling and making amends,” with a restorative rather than punitive focus. Rituals involving symbolic reconciliation, such as the use of palm wine, visiting homes, or group prayers, were seen as means of healing broken relationships, healing divisions and restoring peace. Additionally, the elders expressed that well-being (in the material and non-material senses) is a collective concern: individual misfortune is often interpreted as a possible consequence of communal disharmony, spotlighting the radically interconnected worldviews in *Esan* tradition.

On the comparative question regarding *shalom*, nearly half of the interviewees, particularly those active in Christian congregations, expressed familiarity with the biblical concept, often defining it as “peace” or “blessing.” These respondents drew parallels between *shalom* and *ofure*, observing that both encapsulate wholeness, justice, and the welfare of all members of the community. Among the distinctions noted, a few elders remarked that *shalom* is more abstract and spiritualised in Christian teaching, whereas *ofure* embodies ritual practice and day-to-day social acts, reinforcing peace through tangible, communally enacted processes.

When recounting the practical application of *ofure*, elders shared numerous examples where traditional processes had effectively quelled disputes over land, marriage, or leadership succession. One recalled a notable incident in *Irrua* where a protracted family conflict was resolved through a communal process marked by truth-telling, public apologies, and the symbolic “breaking of the kola nut,” which restored relationships and that enabled cooperative farming *erogha*, benefiting the entire settlement.

Most interviewees were optimistic about the potential benefits of integrating *shalom* and *ofure* in addressing contemporary challenges. They suggested that a hybrid approach, drawing from biblical principles and *Esan* traditions, could provide a more sustainable and culturally resonant path out of violence, economic dislocation, and youth unemployment,

which now affect *Esan* land. Elders stressed the importance of teaching youths Christian and indigenous values, as well as practical instruction in conflict mediation and community-building rituals.

For recommendations to leaders and policymakers, participants advocated for the institutionalisation of *ofure*-based mediation councils in local governance and the integration of *shalom* and *ofure* principles into school curriculum and wider recognition of traditional structures not only for conflict resolution but also for nurturing a sense of shared responsibility for development. Collectively, the interviews highlighted that any sustainable strategy for peace and development in *Esan* land should harness the wisdom of these intersecting traditions, honouring their distinctiveness and their capacity for creative integration.

5.2 Focus Group Discussions with local youth.

The focus group discussion provided valuable insights into local understandings of the realities of peace and well-being among *Esan* community members. Following a warm and clear assurance of confidentiality, participants engaged openly, helping to elucidate individual and collective perceptions of “peace.” When asked to define peace in their own words, most respondents described it as a condition of “quietness,” “freedom from fear,” and “being able to go about one’s business without threat or worry.” Several participants associated personal and communal well-being not only with material prosperity but also with good relationships, trust, and a sense of belonging, echoing core elements found in the biblical concept of *shalom* and the *Esan* idea of *ofure*.

Familiarity with the term *ofure* was universal, and participants connected it to a state of harmony and mutual support, referencing the importance of extended family systems, communal festivals, and age-grade associations in sustaining peace. Most participants admitted to having only a vague or indirect knowledge of *shalom*, often filtered through Christian religious teachings, but found its description similar to their lived ideal of well-being that encompasses more than just survival. In recounting personal experiences, stories of both peace and conflict emerged; elders recalled periods when community disputes were settled amicably by traditional leaders, contrasting with rising instances of youth-related unrest in recent years. Young participants highlighted their active roles in peer mediation but also lamented the loss of respect for elders’ authority and traditional mechanisms due to modernisation and economic pressures.

Discussion of values and challenges revealed strong appreciation for traditions such as communal labour, collective celebration appeal to both ancestral and religious authority in mitigating disputes. However, the most widely cited barriers to peace among today’s youth were unemployment, substance abuse, mistrust of formal justice systems, and political manipulation, factors echoed in recent empirical studies (Uhunmwangho & Epelle 2020; Afrobarometer 2022).

Looking toward the future, participants recommended strengthening community-based dialogue, creating youth economic opportunities, and revitalising traditional conflict resolution practices. Notably, many saw potential for greater integration between religious teachings on *shalom* and indigenous practices of *ofure*, emphasising their synergy as a basis for sustainable peace, provided such integration remains inclusive and adaptable.

5.3 Case Studies: Two Specific Cases Settled at Iruokpen and Uromi Illustrating the Use of *Ofure*

5.3.1 Land Dispute Resolution in Iruokpen

In the town of Iruokpen, a longstanding land dispute between two families, the Eboh and Ighodalo families, had escalated over several years. The conflict involved claims to a large parcel of land that both families believed rightfully belonged to them. Tensions had risen, and the families had taken their grievances to local government authorities, but their attempts at formal mediation had been unsuccessful. The situation became increasingly volatile, leading to public protests and threats of violence.

In response, community elders in Iruokpen, following the principles of *ofure*, intervened to mediate the dispute. The Enijie (traditional rulers) called for a communal gathering, where both families were encouraged to present their grievances publicly, under the watchful eye of the elders. At the gathering, the elders used a series of Esan proverbs that underscored the importance of peace and communal harmony, such as “He who sows peace reaps no quarrels” (*onoko ofure, oi mio ovan*). These words were intended to remind the families of the long-term benefits of reconciliation and the spiritual duty to maintain peace in the community.

The dispute was resolved through a restorative approach, truth-telling, compensation, and the sharing of a symbolic kola nut, a gesture representing mutual forgiveness and the restoration of harmony. The families agreed on a peaceful resolution, with a boundary adjustment to clarify ownership. In the process, the Enijie also prescribed the planting of a “peace tree,” a ritual that symbolized the restoration of harmony and the commitment of both families to uphold *ofure* in future interactions. This case highlighted how *ofure* was used to restore social cohesion by prioritizing dialogue, reconciliation, and a communal sense of responsibility over punitive measures.

5.3.2 Youth Conflict Resolution in Uromi

In *Uromi*, a group of young men from two rival communities, Ekpoma and *Uromi*, had become involved in a violent altercation after a misunderstanding during a local festival. The fight, which initially started as a minor disagreement, quickly escalated into a series of confrontations, resulting in injuries and deepening animosity between the youth groups. The incident not only caused physical harm but also threatened to ignite broader ethnic tensions between the two communities, creating fear and division.

To prevent the situation from spiralling further, the elders in *Uromi*, in consultation with religious leaders, called for a public reconciliation ceremony grounded in the values of *ofure*. The elders convened a peace council that included representatives from both communities, as well as respected spiritual leaders. The council invoked the proverb, “Children of peace must not carry bitterness in their hearts” (*Omon bi ofure ei sabo re dia ki eyan*), to emphasize the necessity of forgiveness and collective healing.

Through a series of restorative practices, the young men involved in the altercation were encouraged to publicly admit their mistakes and seek forgiveness from the community. This was followed by a communal feast, where both sides shared food and drink as a symbolic act of unity and mutual respect. As part of the resolution, the young men participated in a vow of peace ceremony, pledging to honour *ofure* by actively promoting peaceful coexistence in their

future interactions. This case demonstrated the power of *ofure* in restoring not only personal relationships but also broader community cohesion. By focusing on reconciliation rather than punishment, the elders in Uromi used *ofure* to mend the social fabric and address the underlying causes of conflict, fostering a sense of unity that transcended the initial animosity. These two examples from Irukepén and *Uromi* illustrate how *ofure* is used to resolve conflicts in Esan communities. The process involves a deep commitment to communal harmony, justice, and restorative practices, where reconciliation is prioritized over retribution. By integrating these practices into the community's social structure, *ofure* serves as an effective peacebuilding tool, fostering long-term unity and social well-being.

6 Summary of Key Findings

6.1 Holistic Nature of *Ofure*

The elders consistently defined *ofure* not merely as the absence of conflict but as a holistic state marked by communal harmony, relational balance, and both material and spiritual well-being. Ritual practices such as sharing kola nuts, communal prayers, and symbolic reconciliation were highlighted as foundational in sustaining this peace, validating the research objective to identify indigenous mechanisms for holistic societal harmony.

6.2 Relational and Restorative Dynamics

The interviews revealed that *Esan* conflict resolution traditionally prioritises open dialogue, rapid mediation, and restorative justice rooted in truth-telling and making amends instead of punitive measures. This practice supports the objective of identifying culturally embedded conflict management strategies that promote sustainable development.

6.3 Comparative Understanding and Integration

Nearly half of the elders, particularly those active in Christian congregations, demonstrated familiarity with *shalom*, drawing substantive parallels with *ofure*, especially their shared focus on wholeness, justice, and communal well-being. Elders indicated the need for a hybrid model integrating scriptural and indigenous peace concepts, directly addressing the study's goal of assessing the interface and potential synergy between *shalom* and *ofure*.

6.4 Youth Perspectives and Socioeconomic Challenges

Focus group discussions with youth revealed strong resonance with the principles of *ofure*, though appreciation for traditional authority is waning due to modernisation, economic pressures, and rising youth unemployment. The study's methodology effectively captured generational viewpoints, highlighting both appreciation for communal values and the challenges posed by economic and social change.

6.5 Policy and Community Development Recommendations

Both elders and youth advocated for formal institutionalisation of *ofure*-based mediation councils, greater integration of peace concepts in educational curricula, and policy reforms that recognise and empower traditional structures in conflict resolution. These findings affirm the research objective of generating actionable strategies for holistic, sustainable development rooted in intersecting biblical and indigenous frameworks.

6.6 Restoring Harmony: The centrality of spiritual and social alignment in *Shalom* and *Ofure* for holistic societal development in Esanland

This study demonstrates that both *shalom* and *ofure* fundamentally prioritise spiritual and social harmony, viewing genuine peace as rooted in right relationships, with the divine, the community, the land, and oneself. Disrupted spiritual or social bonds undermine collective well-being, making reconciliation, justice, and prosperity inseparable from spiritual and ecological alignment. Especially in Nigeria's context, restoring such harmony is crucial for addressing societal conflict and fragmentation. Thus, sustainable development demands not only economic solutions but also mechanisms for healing spiritual and communal divides, affirming that holistic well-being relies on spiritual coherence and communal solidarity.

6.7 Contrasting Foundations: Spiritual Covenant and Communal Pragmatism in *Shalom* and *Ofure*.

A key finding of this study is the marked divergence in the foundational principles of *shalom* and *ofure*. While *shalom* is inherently emanating from a covenantal relationship initiated by God and anchored in divine justice (Wright 2018), *ofure* is predominantly pragmatic and communal, expressed through the authority of elders, traditional rites, and communal consensus. This distinction shapes each tradition's approach to peace, with *shalom* emphasising spiritual reconciliation and *ofure* prioritising practical social harmony.

7 Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study resonate deeply with contemporary discussions on indigenous peacebuilding and the significance of contextualised development models. Through qualitative interviews with *Esan* elders and focus group discussions with local youth, the research unveiled the multi-layered nature of *ofure*, not simply as a cessation of conflict but as the active cultivation of communal harmony, material well-being, and spiritual balance. Traditional practices, such as the sharing of kola nuts and collective ritual prayers, continue to serve as powerful mechanisms for nurturing these bonds. This holistic understanding mirrors the Sustainable Development Goals' emphasis on "peaceful, just, and inclusive societies," as recognised by the United Nations in their latest SDG Progress Report (UNDP 2023).

Interviews further highlighted the deeply relational and restorative character of *Esan* conflict resolution, which favours open dialogue, community-led mediation, and restitution over punitive sanctions. Such practices echo findings in broader African peace studies, where restorative justice and participatory reconciliation processes have been empirically linked to reduced incidence of violence and higher prospects for societal healing (Afrobarometer 2022).

The elders' emphasis on communal restoration, rather than retribution, directly supports sustainable development, as it maintains social solidarity and trust, two factors consistently associated with collective resilience (UNDP 2022).

A striking aspect of the research is the emerging interface between *shalom* and *ofure*, particularly among Christianized elders. Approximately half of the elder participants actively identified parallels in the two traditions, noting congruence in their focus on justice, right relationships, and wholeness. This is consistent with the observation that a biblical model of *shalom* offers fertile ground for integration with indigenous frameworks, potentially enabling hybrid approaches that are both spiritually resonant and culturally legitimate.

In synthesis, the study concretely affirms that both *shalom* and *ofure* offer holistic pathways to sustainable societal well-being, with restoration of right relationships seen as essential for communal flourishing. Nevertheless, a significant divergence also exists: *shalom* is fundamentally theologically anchored in divine covenant and justice, while *ofure* is pragmatically rooted in communal consensus and tradition. Reconciling these perspectives in development policy will require nuanced, culturally informed strategies that respect both spiritual and social dimensions of peace.

8 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

8.1 Summary

This paper offers an in-depth exploration of the interface between the Old Testament concept of *shalom* and the *Esan* socio-cultural construct of *ofure*, analysing their combined implications for holistic societal development in multi-ethnic contexts such as Nigeria. Both *shalom* and *ofure* are shown to transcend the simple absence of conflict: they encompass comprehensive well-being, justice, relational harmony, and the flourishing of both individuals and communities. Through theological, socio-cultural, and developmental lenses, the paper articulates how these paradigms, despite their distinct historical and cultural roots, converge on essential aspects of peace and sustainable progress.

The statement of the problem reveals how contemporary development approaches in Nigeria remain predominantly centred on GDP growth and other economic measurements, too often sidelining relational, spiritual, and cultural dimensions fundamental to society's health. The marginalisation of non-material factors and indigenous knowledge systems illustrated in the underutilization of both *shalom* and *ofure* has contributed to persistent communal unrest, erosion of social trust, and developmental deficits, especially in places like Edo State (Uhunmwangho & Epelle 2020).

Furthermore, it offers actionable recommendations for scholars, policymakers, community leaders, and faith actors seeking to foster enduring peace and prosperity. In sum, this study affirms that the integration of *shalom* and *ofure* provides a robust, holistic foundation for addressing Nigeria's contemporary challenges, thereby offering a transformative template for societal development rooted in justice, reconciliation, and communal well-being. In sum, the interface of *shalom* and *ofure* could provide a robust lens for societal advancement, emphasising participatory, indigenous, and spiritually grounded practices that go far beyond conventional Western indices.

8.2 Conclusion

This study illuminates the profound potential residing at the intersection of Old Testament *shalom* and the *Esan* construct of *ofure* for envisioning and advancing holistic societal development in Nigeria. The qualitative findings, drawn from rich engagements with *Esan* elders and youth, make clear that *ofure* is markedly expansive in meaning, embodying an ethos of relational harmony, spiritual coherence, and practical justice that mirrors the biblical ideal of *shalom*. Both frameworks recognise peace not as mere absence of strife, but as a positive, active condition comprising right relationships, with the divine, the self, the community, and the environment, thus offering more sustainable and inclusive pathways toward well-being than approaches rooted in material indices alone.

The comparative nature of this work reveals a significant yet complementary distinction, while *shalom* is theologically grounded in a covenantal relationship with God that, for reconciliation and transformative justice, *ofure* is realised through pragmatic communal processes, elder-led mediation, and culturally resonant rituals. This divergence, rather than hindering synthesis, suggests fertile ground for a hybrid model that embraces both spiritual depth and social pragmatism. The participants' perspectives underscore an urgent need for such integrated approaches, as rapid modernization, economic insecurity, and declining traditional authority are increasingly eroding the mechanisms by which communal peace and justice have historically been maintained.

Policy and community recommendations emerging from the study call for the revitalization and institutionalization of *Ofure* based mediation practices, curricular reforms that foreground indigenous and biblical peace concepts, and policy frameworks that empower traditional authority structures in collaboration with faith-based organizations. These proposals align with the broader developmental imperative, enshrined in Sustainable Development Goal 16, of fostering inclusive, peaceful, and just societies. Ultimately, this asserts that holistic development in Nigeria must transcend narrow economic metrics and deliberately cultivate the spiritual, relational, and cultural scaffolding provided by both *shalom* and *ofure*. Only by revitalizing these complementary traditions can communities address not just the symptoms but also the deep-seated causes of conflict, alienation, and societal fragmentation. The study's findings thus serve as a clarion call for scholars, policymakers, religious leaders, and community actors to embrace and operationalize these indigenous and theological resources in forging a pathway to sustainable peace and holistic flourishing.

8.3. Recommendations

Based on these findings, several recommendations are hereby proposed to help bridge the gap between indigenous and scriptural peace concepts, foster holistic societal development, and promote sustainable peace in *Esan* communities and similar contexts:

8.3.1 Institutionalise Hybrid Peace Councils

Establish and formally recognize local mediation councils composed of both traditional elders and faith leaders, with mandates to integrate principles from both *shalom* and *ofure*. This structure can ensure that conflict resolution and peacebuilding processes are inclusive, drawing on spiritual, restorative, and communal mechanisms that resonate across generational and religious divides.

8.3.2 *Integrate Peace Concepts into Educational Curricula*

Revise and expand curricula at primary, secondary, and tertiary levels to explicitly teach the values and practices of both *shalom* and *ofure*. By incorporating these indigenous and scriptural peace paradigms, young people can internalize principles of holistic well-being, justice, restorative dialogue, and shared responsibility, preparing them to navigate and resolve societal challenges constructively.

8.3.3 *Empower Traditional and Religious Structures in Policymaking*

Encourage government and policy actors to formally recognize and empower traditional authorities and faith-based institutions in local governance and development initiatives. Policy reforms should legitimize indigenous mediation methods, involve community elders in decision-making, and support the coexistence of customary and statutory legal systems to ensure culturally grounded and participatory development.

8.3.4 *Promote Youth Engagement and Economic Inclusion*

Develop youth-focused programs that not only address economic needs, such as job creation and vocational training, but also reconnect young people to communal values and conflict resolution traditions. Engaging youth as co-creators of peace initiatives can help restore their trust in traditional structures, adapting ancient wisdom to contemporary challenges and reducing restiveness linked to social and economic disenfranchisement.

8.3.5 *Advanced Intercultural and Interreligious Dialogue*

Foster ongoing platforms for intercultural and interreligious dialogue in *Esan* communities and beyond. By facilitating regular forums and social resources, laying a durable foundation for restorative and inclusive societal growth.

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References

- Adegbile, Wole. 2024. Which Way to Shalom? A Theological Exploration of the Yoruba and Western Foundations for Ethics and Development. *Conspectus The Journal of the South African Theological Seminary*, vol. 37, no. 1. 84-95.
- Adegoke, Damilola and Alvarez, Gloriana Rodriguez. 2025. Peace ontologies, narratives, and epistemes among indigenous communities of Nigeria and Bolivia. *Frontiers in Political Science*.

- Adetoye, Dele. 2022. Indigenous Conflict Management and Peace-building Processes in Nigeria: A Case Study of the Yoruba and Esan People. *African Conflict and Peacebuilding Review*, vol. 12, no. 1. 133-149.
- Afrobarometer. 2022. *Summary of Findings: Nigeria 2022*. Accessed December 16, 2025. <http://afrobarometer.org/publications>
- Aghedo, Iro. 2019. Kinship, Reconciliation, and Social in Esanland. *Anthropological Perspectives on African Societies*, vol. 14, no. 2. 233-247.
- Ajere, Jonathan. 2012. Regional Voluntarism: The Sustainability of Nigerian Afrocentrism” *E-International Relations*. Accessed December 16, 2025. www.e-ir.info
- Akinola, Adeoye O. 2018. Beyond GDP: Rethinking Development Paradigms in Africa. *Journal of Critical African Studies*, vol. 13, no. 1. 44-58
- Akinola, Segun. 2018. Mainstreaming Indigenous Knowledge in Developmental Processes. *Journal of Nigerian Affairs*, vol. 7, no. 1. 22-40.
- Alawode, Olubunmi. 2022. Biblical *Shalom* and Contemporary Justice. *African Theological Review*, vol. 24, no. 2. 55-69.
- Anyamele, Stephen C. 2019. Holistic Approach to Community Development: A Case Study of Nigeria. *Global Journal of Human-Social Research*, vol. 19, no. 1. 35-47.
- AU Peace and Security Council. 2023. *On Community-Based Models in Africa*.
- Braun, Virginia, and Clarke, Victoria. 2019. Reflecting on Reflexive Thematic Analysis. *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, vol. 11, no. 4. 589-597.
- Brueggemann, Walter. 2014. *Peace (Shalom) in the Old Testament*. Oxford Bibliographies.
- Bujo, Benezet. 2005. *African Theology in Its Social Context*. Nairobi: Pauline Publications.
- Ebohon, Sylvanus Idahosa, and Adedeji, Adewunmi. 2022. Contextualising African Indigenous Knowledge Systems in Development Practice. *Journal of African Studies*, vol. 31, no. 2. 98-114.
- Edebiri, J. 2021. *Esan Traditional Concepts and Contemporary Practice*. Benin City: Onobun Publishers.
- ECDP. 2022. *Annual Report of the Esan Documentation Project*. Uromi: ECDP.
- Elugbe, Ben Ohiomamhe, and Omoruyi, E. 2018. Proverbs as Instruments of Peace-building in Esanland. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 23, no. 5. 47-54.
- Esan Cultural Documentation Project. 2022. *Annual Report on Esan Proverbs and Community Rites*. Ekpoma: ECDP Press.
- Gallup. 2023. *Global Emotions Report: Nigeria Profile*. Accessed December 16, 2025. <https://www.gallup.com/analytics/349280/global-emotions-report>
- Harmona Augustus O. and Oyetoro, Taiwo R. 2025. An analysis of Christian perspective on peace communication and conflict resolution in Nigeria. *The Journal of Humanities*, vol. 17, no. 2. 112-127
- Ishola, Tajudeen O. 2022. Beyond the Pedagogy: Indigenous Approaches for Peace Practices in Africa. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 3. 74-82.
- Küng, Hans. 2005. *Global Responsibility: In Search of a New World Ethic*. SCM Press
- Lederach, John Paul. 1997. *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies*. Washington, D.C.: States Institute of Peace Press.
- Membe-Matale, Suzanne. 2015. Ubuntu Theology. *The Ecumenical Review*. vol. 67, no. 2. 273-276.
- Myers, Bre Lynn. 2021. *Walking with the Poor: Principles and Practices of Transformational Development*. Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books.
- NBS [National Bureau of Statistics]. 2023. *Nigeria Social Statistics Report 2023*. Abuja: NBS.
- National Bureau of Employment 2022. *Unemployment and Underemployment Report Q42022*. Accessed December 16, 2025. <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng>
- National Bureau of Statistics. 2023. *Nigeria Digital Economy Index 2021-2023*.
- Obanor, Iyobosa, and Omorodion, F. 2022. Indigenous Mechanisms of Conflict Resolution. *Esan. African Studies Review*, vol. 65, no. 4. 370-392.

- Obayemi, Y. 2021. Indigenous Approaches to Peace and Conflict Resolution in Africa. *African Journal of Conflict Transformation*, vol. 4, no. 2. 67–84.
- Obi, Chukwuemeka. 2022. Decolonising Development Practice in West Africa. *Journal of African Studies*, vol. 15, no. 2. 103–118.
- Odeh, A. 2020. *Ofure* as a Mechanism of Conflict Resolution in *Esanland* of Nigeria. *Journal of African Societies*, vol. 4. 74–89.
- Omoera, Osakwe S. 2019. *Esan* Proverbs, Peace, and Identity. *African Anthropologist*, vol. 26, no. 1&2. 55–75.
- Owan, J. J. 2021. A Biblical Examination of *Shalom*: Implications for Peacebuilding in Contemporary Africa. *Theological Research Review*, vol. 15, no. 3. 210–228.
- Uhunmwuango, Sunday, O., and Epelle, Alafuro. 2020. The Political Economy of Peace and Security in Nigeria: The Case of Edo State. *African Research Review*, vol. 14, no. 2. 102-120.
- UNDP. 2022. *Sustainable Development Goals Report: Goal 16 – Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions*. New York: UNDP.
- United Nations. 2023. *The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2023*. Accessed December 16, 2025. <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2023/>
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). 2022. *Human Development Report 2022*. Accessed December 16, 2025. <http://hdr.undp.org>
- United Nations Development Programme. 2023. *Human Development Report 2023*.
- World Bank. 2023. *Nigeria Economic Update*. Accessed December 16, 2025. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/nigeria/publication/economic-report>
- Wright, Christopher John Hugh. 2004. *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God*. InterVarsity Press.
- Wright, Christopher John Hugh. 2018. *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God*. Downers Grove, IL: IVP Academic.
- Yung, Hwa. 2005. *Mangoes or Bananas? The Quest for an Authentic Asian Christian*. Oxford: Regnum Books.

Appendix I

Interview Guide for *Esan* Elders (*Uromi, Irrua, and Iruekpen*):

1. Understanding *Ofure*:

Can you describe in your own words what *ofure* means to you and how it has been practised in your community throughout your lifetime?

2. Dimensions of Peace:

In your experience, what aspects (such as relationships, justice rituals, well-being) are most important for establishing and maintaining *ofure* in *Esan* communities?

3. Comparative Perspectives:

Are you familiar with the concept of *shalom* from the Bible or Christian teachings? How would you compare or contrast it with the *Esan* idea of *ofure*?

4. Practical Application:

Can you share an example from your community where *ofure* practices or principles helped to resolve conflict, restore peace, and promote development?

5. Integration for Development:

Do you believe that combining the values of *shalom* and *ofure* could help address current social or developmental challenges in *Esanland* or other multi-ethnic communities? Please explain your views.

6. Recommendations for the Future:

What advice or recommendations would you give to community leaders, educators, or policymakers who wish to promote peace and holistic development based on *Esan* and/or biblical principles?

Appendix II

Focus Group Discussion Guide

Introduction

Begin by welcoming the participants and expressing appreciation for their willingness to take part in the discussion. Clearly state the overall purpose of the session, emphasising your interest in exploring perspectives on peace and well-being, as well as the importance of their contributions to this research. Reassure participants of the confidentiality of their responses and explain that any recordings or notes will be used solely for academic purposes, with all identities kept anonymous. Obtain informed consent for participation and permission to record the session. Establish a respectful and open atmosphere by briefly outlining the ground rules: everyone's opinions are valued; there are no right or wrong answers; and respectful, open-minded engagement is expected throughout.

Discussion Topics and Sample Questions.

a. Understanding Peace and Well-being

Invite participants to share their understanding by asking, "How would you describe 'peace' in your own words?" Probe further with questions such as, "What does a peaceful life or community look like to you?" and "Are you familiar with the terms *shalom* or *ofure*, and what do they mean to you?"

b. Personal Experience

Encourage participants to reflect on their lived experiences: "Can you share an example of a time your community experienced peace or conflict?" Ask, "What roles do young people play in promoting peace or resolving conflict in your community?"

c. Values and Challenges

Explore community strengths and barriers by asking, "What values or traditions help to maintain harmony here?" and "What do you see as the major challenges to peace among youths today?"

d. Future Aspirations

Conclude this section by prompting participants to consider solutions: "What changes would you like to see that could better promote peace and well-being for young people?" and "How might traditional and religious concepts, such as *shalom** and *ofure*, be applied to help address current challenges?"

Conclusion

Summarise the key points raised during the discussion, highlighting insights and main themes. Invite any final thoughts or suggestions. Express gratitude once again for their time and perspectives. Explain the next steps of the research and reassure participants about how their input will be used, primarily to inform understanding and propose strategies for peace and well-being in their community.

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BOOK REVIEW

A History of the Bildungsroman

Sarah Graham, (ed.), Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019, pp. 352

Anyone who reads fiction will eventually encounter a Bildungsroman—a novel about a young person facing the challenges of growing up—because it is one of the most popular and enduring genres in literary history.

(Graham 2019: 1)

A History of the Bildungsroman, edited by Sarah Graham and published in 2019, stands as the first comprehensive study of the genre. It offers a historically and geographically expansive survey that meticulously explores its emergence, evolution, and rich literary landscape over more than two centuries. Unlike earlier foundational studies that focused predominantly on the genre's German origins, the volume distinguishes itself as the first comprehensive study to move beyond existing Eurocentric frameworks. This is the volume's most significant contribution, as it fundamentally redefines the Bildungsroman within a global context and demonstrates its broad adaptability across the world literary scholarship.

Graham and the volume's contributors criticize the rigid, tree-like structure of the genre's development. They instead propose a rhizomatic model (Graham 2019: 4), a term borrowed from philosophy, suggesting that the genre developed not from a single root but from multiple, interconnected, and non-hierarchical roots across various cultures and time periods. This framework allows for a more flexible understanding of the genre, emphasizing its ongoing evolution. The collection shifts the focus from a fixed set of formal requirements (e.g., apprenticeship, wandering, finding one's place in society) to the underlying thematic concern: the process of self-formation and the negotiation between individual desire and social expectation. These culturally diverse interwoven roots evolve in distinct yet overlapping ways, roughly from the eighteenth century through modernity. This rhizome is "without origin or end" (Graham 2019: 4), neither clearly emerging from one text or nation nor completely dying off at any one cultural moment.

Intriguingly, the volume's essays do not uniformly embrace the rhizomatic logic, a fact that proves to be a strength. Chapters discussing the German, Russian, and English Bildungsroman (by Todd Kontje, Lina Steiner, and Richard Salmon) often reinforce a more linear model, tracing the genre's descent from Johann Wolfgang von Goethe's *Wilhelm Meister's Apprenticeship* (1795-96). In contrast, other chapters offer crucial counter-narratives, as scholars like Alison Finch, Maroula Joannou, and Meredith Miller instead locate the genre's roots in heterogeneous pre-Goethean forms, such as eighteenth-century romance or Gothic fiction. This latter approach underscores the genre's inherent capacity to articulate dissident gender and sexual identities from its earliest, non-Germanic sources. This internal disagreement among the contributors' genealogical models is not a structural fault, but rather a defining intellectual strength of the volume. It strategically allows the collection to simultaneously present the established, traditionally linear narrative of German-initiated growth alongside fresher, more heterogeneous, and expansive alternatives regarding the genre's enduring development.

A further strength of *A History of the Bildungsroman* (2019) lies in its challenge to the narrow, often restrictive definition of the genre. This volume offers an in-depth analysis of the

evolution of this narrative form and its establishment of significant traditions in various national contexts, particularly Germany (the term's origin), France, Britain, Russia, and the USA, while extending beyond this conventional framework to foreground narratives that have historically been marginalized. The book argues for a much wider and more expansive view of the Bildungsroman, challenging the customary, narrow association of the genre with the journey and social integration of the young, white, middle-class male protagonist. Crucially, a key contribution of the volume demonstrates the genre's diversity by exploring previously overlooked areas and articulating the formative experiences of marginalized subjects such as women, LGBTIQ+ individuals, and postcolonial communities.

Taken together, the volume positions the Bildungsroman as a genre with a deep historical lineage and a dynamic future. Its eleven chapters, written by leading scholars, illuminate the genre's emergence, development, and contemporary relevance. By emphasising the genre's ability to depict resistance and marginality even in the postmillennial period, the collection uncovers its potential for subversive critiques of sexism, racism, imperialism, and homophobia.

A History of the Bildungsroman edited by Sarah Graham is an essential contribution to contemporary literary scholarship. This book has already become and will continue to be perceived as a key reference point in future discussions of the literary genre, compelling scholars to radically expand their understanding of the Bildungsroman's temporal origins, geographical reach, and the diversity of its protagonists.

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